

ABRomics-PF :

A numerical platform on antimicrobial resistance to store, integrate, analyze and share multi-omics data

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Complete project description

3.1 Scientific context and challenges

Antibiotic resistance (ABR) is one of the most important public health issues recognized by major international institutions (Global antimicrobial resistance surveillance system (GLASS) report: early implementation 2017-2018. Geneva: WHO; 2018). Infections due to multidrug resistant (MDR) bacteria are more difficult to treat with few or no treatment options. ABR is also a threat for the future of modern medicine like surgery, organ transplantation or cancer treatment. It is typically a One Health issue with the global circulation of antibiotic resistant isolates and of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) between human, animal and the environment, without frontiers, and it should be considered as such. The evolution of ABR is a complex process with multiple selective forces in different environments. Genome sequences, which contain all the genetic information of an organism, can be used for molecular typing purposes with the highest resolution, the identification of ARGs and their genetic supports as well as mutations leading to a decrease in antibiotic susceptibility. Reinforcing the sharing of high-quality sequence data for diagnostic and epidemiological applications, together with interoperable and curated metadata, which can be integrated with other omics data, is a key requirement for understanding the complexity of spatiotemporal patterns of pathogen and ARGs transmission between compartments (human, animal, food, environment). There is an urgent need to reinforce collaborations between public health studies, clinical microbiology and fundamental research, as well as between scientists of the human, animal and environmental sectors.

Bacterial Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) is entering the clinical practice in molecular epidemiology in the hospital context, but also in surveillance in the environmental and animal health sectors. Its combination with epidemiological information can enable tracking transmissions of outbreaks and identifying a source of contamination. A One Health approach is also needed to identify and quantify transmissions of strains, plasmids and genes between the three sectors. It allows the reconstruction of the emergence of high risk lineages. However, to be able to analyze the future emergence of new strains or genes in France, it is necessary to keep track of circulating isolates. Today, if more systematic genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis allow to partially address such major issues (as it is evident in the

case of the SARS-COV-2 pandemic), **data sharing and comparison across centres, together with standardization of analytical workflows remain major bottlenecks.**

The availability and quality of DNA sequences (raw data as FASTQ files and genome assembly) and their associated metadata are absolutely crucial. WGS data are expected to be submitted to international sequence repositories (EBI-ENA, DDBJ and NCBI-SRA), but multiple causes such as the Open data policies of these data repositories (ownership reflex!), and/or lack of time or expertise for engaging efforts in the data annotation and deposition, limit the sharing of the genomic data. In addition, associated data are often restricted to some predetermined features (i.e., phenotypic data like MICs (Minimal Inhibitory Concentrations) could not be easily provided). WGS are frequently only stored locally in clinical or research laboratories, with the risk to be lost. Therefore, there is an urgent need to **provide the community with a user-friendly platform to store and share genomic information together with their metadata**, and which will also serve as a **data brokering hub to ease the submission of data sequences into international repositories.**

Software analysis of DNA sequences are rapidly evolving and require strong expertise, especially when the number of analyzed sequences is huge. Indeed, the exploitation of the different data types requires reliable software tools, effective and reproducible workflows, standardized software environments, and powerful computing resources. Analysis tools are essential to produce secondary research data and new knowledge for clinical and public health microbiologists. These tools should provide information on the submitted isolates (or the community for metagenomics data) such as taxonomy, plasmid and ARGs content, virulome, and information on the relations with other isolates submitted in the database, for example to infer hypothetical transmissions. Moreover, the broader research community needs to perform more sophisticated analyses on stored information, which goes beyond automated surveillance (i.e., complex transmission models), ideally by integrating other types of omics data (proteomics, metabolomics, etc).

Several specific platforms offering both similar and complementary functionalities have been set up in different countries (NCBI Pathogen Detection: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogens>; Swiss Pathogen Surveillance Platform, SPSP: <https://www.spsp.ch>; Pathogenwatch: <https://pathogen.watch>; Enterobase: <https://enterobase.warwick.ac.uk>; Center for Genomic Epidemiology, CGE: <http://www.genomicepidemiology.org>; IRIDA: <https://www.irida.ca>; PATRIC: <https://www.patricbrc.org>). They have been designed with different objectives for a local use like the SPSP and IRIDA platforms, or an international use like CGE and PATRIC. Some tools are focusing on epidemiological data (MLST, genomic variations) of important pathogens like BIGSdb or Enterobase. Although these web-based platforms provide first important steps, data analysis remains somewhat static and does not allow prediction of the dynamic properties of an epidemic or outbreak. More specifically, they generally lack user-friendly semi-automated pipelines (i.e., for human expert data quality control), interoperable analytical procedures and bioinformatics services allowing to integrate multi-omics data, communication and data exchange between instances (epidemiologists, clinical microbiologists, and researchers) through customizable access controls (including restrictive jurisdictional data sharing policies).

3.2 Objectives

The ABRomics-PF project aims at developing a secure One Health cross-sectorial online platform to make accessible bacterial infectious disease (meta)genomics data and their associated clinical and epidemiological metadata to a meta-network of researchers including epidemiologists, clinical microbiologists, and the broader research community.

The platform will address two main objectives:

- Establish a repository of structured, interoperable, standardized and well-annotated multi-omics microbiological data from human, animal and environmental origins, with tailored mathematical and bioinformatic tools, that can be used to answer **research questions related to ABR which could not be addressed without such a platform.**
- Establish a shared **platform to assist ABR surveillance** across human and veterinary medicine, also including environmental and food isolates, to allow transmission and outbreak surveillance of pathogens in near real-time, with actionable results for public health authorities. FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data management procedures will allow retrospective studies.

The combination of these two objectives is unique to the ABRomics-PF: linking field investigation in multiple sectors to fundamental research will allow us to address the most urgent clinical and environmental issues using an up-to-date arsenal of mathematical and bioinformatic tools.

According to these two objectives, ABRomics will provide a unique tool to store and analyze data to the diverse communities addressing the antibiotic resistance issue as summarized in the following table:

Users	Application
Microbiology lab in veterinary clinic and medium size hospital	Storage and analysis of WGS for isolate characterization, outbreak investigation and source identification
Microbiology lab in University Hospitals	Omics data storage and analysis for clinical research
Public health laboratory: NRC (human), ANSES (animal, food, environment)	Global and One Health surveillance of AMR, strains and ARG transmission
Environmental research	One health analysis of emergence and dissemination of AMR by combining genomic and metagenomic data
Public health agencies	Integrating omics data for global surveillance and retrospective analysis
Diagnostic research	Omics resource and link with biobanks for the development of new methods for AST
Therapeutic research	Omics resource and link with biobanks for developing efficient therapeutic strategies and anticipating resistance

Fundamental research	Platform for omics data management, sharing and analysis. It will offer an environment (tools and multi omics data) to answer research questions through integrative bioinformatics procedures. Facilitate interactions with clinicians and field investigators.
Bioinformatician and modelers	Platform to develop and disseminate new methods and access to multi-omics data.

Table 1. Main applications of the ABRomics-PF for a diversity of users

The ABRomics-PF will be made of an IT infrastructure for the storage and management of heterogeneous data and will provide bioinformatics tools, including (semi)automatic pipelines and advanced customize tools for more advanced users.

The targeted audiences of the ABRomics-PF will be:

- Environmental and medical (Human and veterinary) microbiologists
- Healthcare structures, infection prevention and control (IPC) practitioners and clinicians
- Epidemiologists
- Researchers in fundamental microbiology
- Public health institutions
- Industries

By allowing data sharing, the ABRomics-PF aims to stimulate and facilitate common projects across communities not yet used to interact, and therefore to better address the One Health dimension of antibiotic resistance. This national platform will also allow to store and share omics data from international projects involving French partners. Together with the inclusion of genomic data from international depositories, the ABRomics-PF will allow data analysis in the global context of AMR.

Outcomes:

- ⇒ Characterization of outbreaks and source identification
- ⇒ Cross sectorial transmissions
- ⇒ Identification of cross sectorial shuttles involved in AMR spread
- ⇒ New resistance mechanisms
- ⇒ One health genomic epidemiology

Figure 1. Flow chart of the workflow from data production to outcomes for Use Case 1, highlighting the One Health dimension of the ABRomics project.

In close collaboration with the European bioinformatics infrastructure ELIXIR (www.elixir-europe.org), in which IFB is actively participating as the French node, best practices will drive the implementation of the ABRomics-PF: data standards, controlled vocabularies and ontologies to ensure high quality microbiological, clinical and epidemiological metadata, FAIR data, and maintainability of software and analysis pipelines. The ABRomics-PF will allow users to perform localized or remote analyses, while simultaneously supporting data sharing and synchronization across the consortium members according to the defined access rights, together with sequence deposition to centralized repositories (national and international) through data brokering procedures.

At the European level, ABROmics partners, in particular directors from NRC and ANSES laboratories, are involved in ECDC (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/>) and EFSA (<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/>) projects for implementing WGS in surveillance, including the European Antimicrobial Resistance Genes Surveillance Network (EURGen-Net, <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/about-us/who-we-work/disease-and-laboratory-networks/EURGen-ne>). The ABROmics-PF will use data format to facilitate and automate the transfer of genomic and associated (meta)data with these international agencies.

3.3 Description of the project

Given the funds allocated to the present call (2 M€ for the 3 objectives), we have built our proposal to mutualize efforts on the current IFB's IT infrastructure and the MuDiS4LS project (Equipex+/PIA3 call) which will start in February 2021 (cf. **Appendix 5**). This is a major benefit for the ABRomics consortium as most of the financing will be dedicated to the proposed technological developments which address the needs of ABR surveillance and research.

The ABRomics-PF will be made of three essential components as shown in the Fig1 and Fig2 of **Appendix 1**:

- an **IT infrastructure** with high capacity of data storage and data analysis, accessible to users under defined rules (free to strict depending on the sensitivity of the data), and offering a general software environment, both HPC and Cloud environments (WP1)
- **integrated multi-omics microbiological databases** for the Human-Animal-Environment sectors, which will be interoperable with each other and with epidemiological resources and databases such as health data depositories of the French University-Hospitals Centres (CHU), the national health data system and the Health Data Hub (WP2). This component will also include standard tools and pipelines for (semi) automatic analysis of NGS data from pathogenic strains.
- **mathematical and bioinformatics tools** to analyze and interpret user-submitted multi-omics data, and to model the evolution of antibiotic resistance, the transmission and dissemination of clones and genes within and between sectors (WP3).

Dedicated use-cases will be implemented for demonstrating the power of ABRomics-PF on ABR fight (WP4). The platform will provide an integrated and secured environment to potentiate the interpretation of results by specialists, and their dissemination towards the general public. A common **open Web portal** (WP6), transversal to the three technological components (WP1, WP2, WP3), to the coordination of the project (WP0), and to the training and outreach activities of the ABRomics-PF (WP5), will be developed.

The following sections give a general overview of the 6 ABRomics-PF project work packages.

WPO. Management and coordination of the project

Co-coordination

1. Claudine Médigue (co director of the French Bioinformatics Institute)
2. Philippe Glaser (PI at Institut Pasteur)
3. Jacques van Helden (co director of the French Bioinformatics Institute)
4. Richard Bonnet (NRC antibiotic resistances)

Objectives

WPO aims at managing and coordinating the project as a whole.

1. Write the consortium agreement
2. Establish the project committees: steering committee, user committee, scientific advisory board (SAB)
3. Organise the coordination between work packages and monitor and manage the risk of the project (cf. section 3.5)
4. Define the rules of access to the platform
5. Organise the consortium meetings (kick-off, annual general meetings)
6. Develop the sustainability of the platform
7. Assess and report the project impact (cf. section 3.4)

Description

Meeting the ambitious goals of the platform will require a well-structured governance in order to ensure the coordination between the 50 partner teams, a fair allocation of the funding between work packages and participating teams, according to their involvement, the alignment between the multi-omics platform and the user needs, and the strategic choices to cope with the evolution of the domain. This coordination will rely first on a **Steering Committee** composed of the project heads as well as one representative per work package (chosen among the co-coordinators). It will be responsible for the (1) management and administration of IFB-core, (2) presentation of an annual report (scientific and financial) to the board of directors including propositions of orientations, (3) preparation, supervision and execution of the scientific programme with regard to the available budget, (4) implementation of the ABRomics-PF funding model. The SC will meet twice a week.

Three committees in charge of the scientific strategy and policy will help the SC:

Board of directors. Representatives of the supervisory authorities constituted in collaboration with the two thematic research alliances Aviesan and AllEnvi. It approves ABRomics's scientific programme and budget. This committee will meet at least once a year.

User and stakeholder committee, including representatives of the different types of users : clinicians, infectiologists, microbiologists, national public health institutions, patient associations (e.g. Vaincre la Mucoviscidose) and from the three sectors: human and animal health and the environment. To ensure the coherence between the different AMR networks, the coordinator of the PROMISE project will also be a member of the User and stakeholder committee. It will define the main strategic orientations with regard to the Scientific Advisory Board report, and will discuss new orientations as often as necessary (by

email or TC). It will meet once a year. On the other hand one of the two ABRomics coordinators will be a member of the PROMISE scientific advisory board and invited to its general assembly.

Scientific and ethical advisory board, composed of international experts, as well as representatives of ethics committees. It will review ABRomics-PF actions, provide advice that will be taken into account during the revision of the annual work plan, and assist the SC on legal, ethical and societal issues related to the protection of sensitive data. The SAB will meet every 2 years.

Moreover an **operational cell**, composed of the PI of each work-package, will gather once a month to take stock of the progresses of the actions, assess impact, and propose adapted measures to meet the objectives of the projects and the expectations of the three committees. Working groups gathering members of the consortium involved in the various work packages and use cases will meet regularly.

Finally, beyond the four-years funding allocated by the French Ministry, the sustainability of the ABRomics-PF will rely on the engagement of IFB supervisory authorities and partner organisms and on a funding model that will include pricing strategy and contractual resources (with academic and industrial partners).

WPO tasks

Task	Task title	Task description	Person(s) involved [team]
T0.1	Establishment of the committees (SAB, user committee)		<i>Philippe Glaser [IP; EERA] & Claudine Médigue [IFB; MicroScope PF]</i>
T0.2	Writing of the consortium agreement		<i>Richard Bonnet [CNR] & Claudine Médigue [IFB; MicroScope PF] & CDD 50% [ABRomics]</i>
T0.3	Administrative and financial management of the project		<i>Jacques van Helden [IFB; ATGC PF] & Valentin Saint Leger [IFB-core]</i>
T0.4	Support to the scientific coordination		<i>Claudine Médigue [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Philippe Glaser [IP; EERA]</i>
T0.5	Organisation of the consortium events (AGM, WP meetings, ...)		<i>Reines Bouyssie [IP; EERA] & Philippe Glaser [IP; EERA] & Valentin Saint Leger [IFB-core] & Sam Keuchkerian [IFB; SNM]</i>
T0.6	Setting-up of a funding model of the ABRomics-PF		<i>Claudine Médigue [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Pascal Kalhem [IFB; SNM]</i>

WPO deliverables

		Delivery month
D0.1	Kick-off meeting (AGM 0)	1
D0.2	Scientific and financial report	13

WP1. Computing architecture (obj1)

Co-coordination

1. Gildas Le Corguillé (PI of the IFB National Network of Computing Resources)
2. Geoffrey Detrez (DSI at Institut Pasteur)
3. Fabien Mareuil (Institut Pasteur, Hub Bioinfo)
4. Christophe Blanchet (PI fo the IFB National Network of Computing Resources)

Objectives

The WP1 aims at providing the ABRomics consortium with the computing infrastructure and software environment, in link with the data providers infrastructures located in hospitals and NRC sites and from a diversity of users of ABRomics. It will be in charge of choosing adapted solutions to match the needs of the different components of the infrastructure: HTC clusters, and cloud with virtual machines and containers. It will also address the ABRomics-PF access of end-users with very different computer skills by implementing different types of interfaces: Unix command line, Application Programmatic Interfaces (API), Galaxy platform, interfaces for inexperienced users. Such specialized customised-environments will help to answer the needs of the different end-user communities. Finally, portable solutions will bring software environments to the sensible data rather than the opposite.

Description

Providing computing infrastructure capacity to the ABRomics platform requires both to set up the integrated database and scalable customized analysis environments for the data processing. The consortium will benefit of the strength of IFB's National Network Computing Resources (IFB NNCR), both in terms of mutualisation of resources and expertises (cf. section 2.1). Moreover, ABRomics will also rely on the developments and computer equipment planned in the IFB's MuDIS4LS recently-accepted project (Mutualised Digital Spaces for FAIR data in Life and Health Science), and financed for 8 years (2021-2028).

The main challenges related to the computing infrastructure are to:

1. set up protocols to gather the data from many sources (external genomic and other omics databases, CHU, NRC..) and host the integrated database (link with WP2).
2. define best practices to deploy the specific analysis environments, and provide the required computing resources (link with WP2 and WP3)
3. organize trainings and hackathons to ensure adoption of the ABRomics-PF (WP5)
4. host the platform web portal, with the required quality of service (link with WP6). Access-rights of the ABRomics-PF end-users will be managed by WP6.

Collecting data from different sources distributed over the country and with potential access-security constraints means that the ABRomics-PF infrastructure needs efficient Internet connections between the data provider and the data centers that will host the ABRomics-PF resources. Indeed, IFB's core resources are hosted in national datacenters (CC-IN2P3, IDRIS) with such high-performance connectivity (10 gbps) to the French national Internet backbone (Renater). The consortium also plans to adapt the general framework proposed in the MuDiS4LS project to the needs of the users community working on ABR: transformation of data management into a dynamic process though the implementation of machine actionable DMP (maDMP) which will handle data transfers at its different stages (production, analysis, public opening). Moreover, the integration of multi-omics data in the ABRomics data warehouse (cf. WP2),

requires high storage capacity and performances, together with high computing capacities for the processing of numerous and often large data files with different formats, and of intensive meta-data queries. The work performed in WP1 will constitute the basic components of a future ABRomics-PF data lake: in this context, competences of the Institut Pasteur IT department in the development of the Owey data lake (**Appendix 6.2**) will be extremely valuable.

To address the broad range of users' computer science skills (bioinformaticians, experimental biologists and clinicians), the ABRomics-PF will provide different interfaces upon the set of tools and pipelines (WP2 and WP3): command line, Jupyter notebooks, Galaxy, and web portal (developed with WP6). Galaxy already offers a secure pillar to deploy a ready-to-use working environment: authentication, secure dataset management, tool descriptions, dependencies, modularity, parallelization on HPC systems, etc. However, in order to offer tools, workflows and computing resources to clinicians with less time and skills in computing science, the WP1 will develop a seamless customized easy-to-use layer on top of Galaxy in order to take advantage of the Galaxy features. We will base our development on existing projects developed within the ABRomics consortium (e.g.: ngphylogeny.fr, ariaweb.pasteur.fr, mogi.readthedocs.io). The backend will be handled by the French Galaxy instance: usegalaxy.fr operated by the IFB. For sensible data (human data, patient, etc.) that cannot be disclosed, we will develop, jointly with the MuDI4LS project portable solutions based on virtual machines and container technologies (Docker, Singularity).

WP1 Tasks

Task	Task title	Task description	Person(s) involved [team]
T1.1	Definition of the infrastructure requirements, integration plan, and machine actionable DMP dedicated to ANR R&D projects	In link with WP2, WP3 & WP6	<i>Paulette Lieby [IFB Core] & CDD WP1.3 [ABRomics]</i>
T1.2	Integration and operations of the infrastructure (Provide accesses to computing facilities)	- HPC and Cloud infrastructures - Web application hosting	<i>Nicole Charrière [IFB Core] & Christophe Blanchet [IFB Core] & Julien Seiler [IFB; BigEst PF] & Gildas Le Corguillé [IFB; ABiMS PF] & CDD WP1.3 [ABRomics]</i>
T1.3	Provide and build user interfaces to access the computing infrastructure	- Tools and workflow within the HPC infrastructure - Galaxy instance with tools, workflows and databanks	<i>Gildas Le Corguillé [IFB; ABiMS PF] & Thomas Chaussepied [IFB Core] & Fabien Mareuil [IFB; Pasteur] & Julien Seiler [IFB; BigEst PF] & CDD WP1.2 20% [ABRomics] & Pierre Pericard [IFB; Bilille PF]</i>
T1.4	Develop a user-friendly web interface on top of Galaxy	- A web interface which will use the Galaxy API	<i>Fabien Mareuil [IFB; Pasteur] & Gildas Le Corguillé [IFB; ABiMS PF] & CDD WP1.2 50% [ABRomics] & CDD WP6 25% [ABRomics] & Thomas Chaussepied [IFB Core] & Julien Seiler [IFB; BigEst PF] & Pierre Pericard [IFB; Bilille PF]</i>

T1.5	Integrated database (Data warehouse hosting)	- A data warehouse for data collection, data sharing, data annotation and access security management	<i>Geoffrey Detrez [Pasteur] & Philippe Lehours [CNR Bordeaux] & Claudine Medigue [IFB; Microscope PF] & CDD WP1.1 [ABRomics]</i>
T1.6	Develop and provide portable solutions to bring compute to the data for sensible data	- Containers with all the necessary tools - Galaxy docker container with all the necessary tools	<i>Christophe Blanchet [IFB Core] & Gildas Le Corguillé [IFB; ABiMS PF] & Fabien Mareuil [IFB; Pasteur] & Thomas Chaussepied [IFB Core] & CDD WP6 25% [ABRomics] & Julien Seiler [IFB; BigEst PF] & Pierre Pericard [IFB; Bilille PF] & CDD WP1.3 [ABRomics]</i>

WP1 Deliverables

		Delivery month
D1.1	Definition of the infrastructure plan according to the requirements related to the integrated database and bioinformatics tools	12
D1.2	Development infrastructure according to the first round of database and tools requirements (beta version of ABRomics-PF)	12
D1.3	Galaxy subdomain within usegalaxy.fr	12
D1.4	Initial production infrastructure	24
D1.5	A user-friendly minimalist web interface on top of usegalaxy.fr based on the Galaxy API	33
D1.6	Containers with all the necessary tools including Galaxy docker containers for sensible data	36
D1.7	Advanced production infrastructure improved with new database and tools features	48

WP1 GANTT chart

WP2. Integrated multi-omics microbiological database (obj. 2)

Co-coordination

- Amine Ghozlane (Institut Pasteur, Hub Bioinfo)
- Etienne Ruppé (MCU-PH microbiology, Hôpitaux de Paris)
- Richard Bonnet (NRC antibiotic resistances)
- Hervé Ménager (Institut Pasteur, Hub Bioinfo)

Objectives

The main objective of this WP is to collect, standardize, organise, integrate and give access to the different types of multi-omics data relevant to ABR. Specifically, this WP will aim to:

1. Gather data from external genomic and other omics databases, as well as the associated metadata and data relevant for surveillance purposes from human, animal and environmental origins
2. Develop and run semi-automatic workflows for the standard data processing and annotation. These will combine automatic processing and human interventions (quality control, informed processing choices, etc.)
3. Provide users with user-friendly interfaces which will be developed in close collaboration with WP6 to explore the results of standards analysis
4. Identify, cure, and complement the knowledge databases relevant to antimicrobial resistance and their associated metadata, following the FAIR standards
5. Manage the accesses to the data in the shared ABRomics database and the project-specific data spaces (in collaboration with WP6).
6. Ensure interoperability with sample collections

Description

Building the ABRomics data warehouse (Fig1 Appendix 1 & Fig3 Appendix 2 WP2). It will first host data (sequencing data and their associated metadata) contributed by members of the consortium and external users.

The criteria for inclusion of data will be:

- Relevance for research and surveillance of antibiotic resistance
- Data will be submitted to a quality check following their submission. Data below a quality threshold will be rejected.
- Data should be in a compatible format
- Minimal set of information on the biological sample (mandatory information)
- Agreement with ethical issues

Detailed criteria for data inclusion, harmonization and raw data processing can be found in the new Appendix "Genomics&MetagenomicsData-in-ABRomics".

Data will be submitted either through a dedicated web interface (WP6) and/or by secure network transfer (WP1). They will be compatible with the multiple types of data on biological samples: genomic, metagenomic, phenotypic data, especially Antimicrobial Sensitivity Tests (AST), other omics data and the associated metadata. The usability of these data will require an agreement on their format and metadata

specifications: this will be done consistently with the standards defined by international projects (i.e., NCBI Pathogen detection, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogens/>). Indeed, submission of new data sequences and their associated metadata will lead to the creation of a **bioproject space with restricted accesses** (WP1 & WP6) and a Data Management Plan (DMP) allowing researchers to design the data path and their accessibility to other users throughout the research lifecycle: dynamic resource allocation (modification of the data volumes, inclusion of new data), modification of the collaborators, etc. (cf. WP1 & WP6). Thus, users could keep their data private during a period of time (i.e., embargo during the pre-publication exploitation phase) before depositing them in the shared data space of the ABR-omics data warehouse.

For comparative analysis purposes, the **shared space of the ABRomics database** will store genomic (meta)data coming from international repositories (ENA, NCBI) or specific databases (i.e., Enterobase). Starting with available complete genome sequences of bacterial species of interest for ABR (Enterobacterales, *Pseudomonas*, *Acinetobacter*, *Enterococcus*, *Staphylococcus*, *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Helicobacter*), we will build reference pan-genomes with their associated gene families that will considerably ease further analysis on core and accessory gene sets. Procedures to automatically update these pan-genomes and gene families will also be defined. In this context, data exchanges with other national dataverses (during the exploitation phase) and international repositories will be based on the data brokering services set-up by IFB.

The reference databases and repositories relevant for ABR analysis, which the standard annotation pipelines relies on (see below), will be imported in the shared space of the ABRomics database and cross-exchanges will ensure their updates (i.e., Taxonomy, MLST, cgMLST, plasmids, transposons, virulence factors and serotypes). Specific attention will be paid on the antibiotic resistance genes collected in databases hosted by members of our consortium (see **Appendix 6.1**), which gather published data and data from popular databases such as NDARO (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogens/antimicrobial-resistance/>), ResFinder_DB (https://bitbucket.org/genomicepidemiology/resfinder_db), and CARD (<https://card.mcmaster.ca>). WP2 will merge and harmonize data on known ABR genes, and **curate new resistance genes to enrich the ABRomics-PF database**. This will be done following the efforts of metadata inclusion initiated by the ResFinder team (Bortolaia *et al.*, 2020; <http://doi.org/10.1093/jac/dkaa345>) and the standardization/ interoperability initiatives performed in the context of a partnership between coordinators of this WP2 and holders of international databases (Joint Research Center, European Commission). Indeed, based on the skills and long-term experience of the national reference centers, and the one of others researchers working on ABR mechanisms, the ABRomics-PF will offer a **knowledge graph for resistance genes**. Ontology-based data integration has proven successful in providing human and machine-actionable means to tackle Life Science data diversity and distribution challenges (Kamdar, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-019-0162-5>), while implementing and fostering FAIR principles.

In ABRomics-PF, newly predicted genes resulting from WP4 use cases will be curated leveraging existing ontologies (e.g., host-microbiome ontology OHMI (Yongqun, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13326-019-0217-1>), ontology for antibiotic resistance ARO (Alcock, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz935>), pharmaco-vigilance, <https://inab-certh.github.io/OpenPVSignal/>, etc.) and feed the ABRomics FAIR knowledge graph. This knowledge graph will strongly contribute to the discoverability and reuse of common antibiotic-resistance digital resources. Given its graph-based structure, it will naturally connect with WP3 by (i) providing graph-based information to feed modeling algorithms and (ii) continuously ingesting novel genomic or environmental knowledge.

Standard analysis workflows: Following an evaluation of the up-to-date softwares used in the context of genomic epidemiology (typing, phenotyping, phylogeny, association studies), we will develop several workflows that will interconnect the tools to ensure a swift automated processing of the omic data. They should allow a spatio-temporal surveillance of ABR determinants and their bacterial hosts from genomics

and metagenomic data generated from environmental, animal or clinical samples. In this perspective, a benchmark of existing tools will be undertaken to select for the most performant solutions.

Briefly, users will be able to run standard workflows for the preprocessing and automatic annotation of their omics data (cf. **Fig4 WP2 Appendix 2**). The automated workflows will be adapted not only to annotate newly sequenced genomes, but also to re-annotate selected genomes downloaded from the international databases (see above). This process will allow an incremental and consistent annotation of the data stored in the data warehouse. A FAIR management of the shared data will enable regular re-analysis of user data, as new knowledge becomes available.

As explained in section 2.2, the ABRomics-PF will be restricted to the processing and annotation of non-sensitive data (at least for the 2 first years). Portable solutions to bring software environments to the sensible data will allow an external cross analysis of data stored in ABRomics on biological samples described with health and personal data. However, in the medium term, the link with clinical, temporal and geographical data will bring a significant added value in terms of AMR surveillance.

Links between the ABRomics-PF and the data warehouse developed in the framework of the PROMISE project. These two data warehouses are complementary as they will store and analyse different types of data. Typically, the PROMISE data warehouse will deal with aggregated data collected by different networks and ABRomics with individual samples as depicted in the figure below. We therefore expect a strong synergy between the two projects.

Figure 2. Complementarity and interactions between the PROMISE data warehouse and ABRomics.

Links between the ABRomics-PF and the archived biological material. Access to biological material is essential to validate hypotheses and to perform research projects based on omics data and their analyses.

ABRomics will not perform biobanking, but it will facilitate the access to biological material to promote collaborative projects. For this reason, biobanking information will be included in the metadata, which should be submitted together with Omics data. The use of common identifiers will allow interoperability between ABRomics and strain collections databases.

Public health, collections and research laboratories have different strategies and requirements for the storage of bacterial isolates. For instance, in the case of the NRC of antibiotic resistance, each of the 4 partner laboratories holds its own collections of strains with internal electronic records and storage conditions in accordance with the quality recommendations in force. The directories contain mainly microbiological data (nature of resistance mechanisms, MICs, genotypes...). Individual clinical data are confined to the computerized databases of the university hospitals sending the isolates. At the Institut Pasteur, the data management system of our biocollection facilities, including NRCs and Biological Resource Center CRBIP, records biological material associated metadata and creates and maintains a link between biosamples, associated metadata and sequence data. For example the CRBIP maintains collections of microbiological materials and associated information through a laboratory information management system. Several checks are carried out in order to ensure the conformity of the biological material with the properties described by the depositor. Information (i.e., biological material characteristics, metadata, sequence data and genomes' accession number) is gathered in a dedicated database and a catalog covering each of the collections is available at <https://catalogue-crbip.pasteur.fr/> to facilitates access to these biological resources for clients, researchers, etc. This ensures that these biological resources remain available to researchers or industry in the future for sustainable use.

WP2 Tasks

Task	Task title	Task description	Person(s) involved [team]
T2.1	Define Bioproject spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - database structuration of the user data including samples with associated metadata, AST data, raw sequencing data, and the data generated from the bioinformatic tools - definition of a Data Management Plan and its evolution during the life cycle of a research project (with WP1) 	<i>Aurélien Birer [CNR-RA] & Bogdan Iorga [ICSN-CNRS] &</i>
T2.2	Benchmarking of existing analysis tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - selection of standard data sets (genomic and metagenomic) - evaluation of the up-to-date softwares used in the context of genomic epidemiology (typing, phenotyping, phylogeny, GWAS) 	<i>Federica Palma [Pasteur] & Sylvain Brisse [Pasteur] & Julien Guglielmini [Pasteur] & Bogdan Iorga [ICSN-CNRS] & Geneviève Héry-Arnaud [INSERM] & Lourdes Veloz-Suarez [INSERM] & Olivier Barraud [INSERM]</i>

T2.3	Built the ABRomics-PF data warehouse: genomic data and associated metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collect genomic data sequences and metadata from international repositories (i.e., NCBI) and/or dedicated databases (i.e., EnteroBase) of priority pathogens (https://www.who.int/news/item/27-02-2017-who-publishes-list-of-bacteria-for-which-new-antibiotics-are-urgently-needed) - Built their pangenome graphs (with WP3) 	<i>Bogdan Iorga [ICSN-CNRS] & Amine Ghozlane [Pasteur]</i>
T2.4	Built the ABRomics-PF data warehouse: ABR resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collect databases relevant to antimicrobial resistance (e.g. NDARO, ResFinder_DB, AMRFinder, EFINDER, BLDB, and CARD), to virulence (VFDB), to plasmid and other mobile elements detection (e.g. PlasmidFinder, pMLST, CONJscan-T4SSscan, COPLA, MobileElementFinder), to serotype prediction and molecular typing (fimH, spa, MLST, cgMLST) - Improve and curate knowledge on resistance genes based on previous works and competences of the consortium (ResFinder4) - Define processes to update the data warehouse content according to updates of the collected databases - Collaborate with the main international data centers (EBI, NCBI) in order to ensure the sustainability of the cross-references 	<i>Richard Bonnet [CNR-RA] & Aurélien Birer [CNR-RA] & Federica Palma [Pasteur] & Sylvain Brisse [Pasteur] & Bryan Brancotte [Pasteur] & Youssef Ghorbal [Pasteur] & Brice Raffestin [Pasteur] & Sebastien Bridel [Pasteur] & Benoit Doublet [INRAE] & Sébastien Leclercq [INRAE] & Bogdan Iorga [ICSN-CNRS] & Vincent Cattoir [CNR-RA] & Etienne Ruppé (INSERM) & Amine Ghozlane [Pasteur]</i>
T2.5	Knowledge graph for interlinked ABR data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proposing a collection of competency questions from WP3 modelling activities and WP4 use cases - Benchmarking existing standards and ontologies inline with WP3 and WP4 - Proposing and implementing a collection of queries serving WP3 and WP3 modelers - Assembling and serving an 	<i>Alban Gaignard [IFB, BiRD PF] & Hervé Ménager [Pasteur, IFB] & Samuel Chaffron [IFB; BiRD PF] & Pierre Larmande [IRD, IFB]</i>

		integrated Knowledge Graph based on WP2 data sources	
T2.6	Implement workflows for standard data analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Define format for data submission and mandatory information on the data (experimental information and metadata on the biological samples) ensuring the semantic interoperability between the different omics data types : genes, proteins, enzymes, reactions, ... (e.g. possibility to cross-reference a gene and its product). - Selection and integration of relevant standard analysis tools in automatic pipelines for quality control, genomic and metagenomic assembly, plasmid detection and typing (mobilome), (meta)genomolecular typing, phylogenomics inference, cgMLST profile, SNPs and resistance virulome and antibiotic resistome virulence calling, association studies (GWAS). - Develop workflows aiming at tracing the spatial, biological and temporal circulation of ARG and elements related to ABR (e.g., nextstrain or microreact) 	<p><i>Richard Bonnet [CNR-RA] & Philippe Glaser (EERA-Pasteur) & Federica Palma [Pasteur] & Sylvain Brisse [Pasteur] & Virginie Passet [Pasteur] & Christiane Bouchier [Pasteur] & Benoit Doublet [INRAE] & Sébastien Leclercq [INRAE] & Bogdan Iorga [ICSN-CNRS] & Laurent Jacob [IFB; LBBE] & Vincent Cattoir [CNR-RA] & Philippe Bulet [BioPark] & Amine Ghozlane [Pasteur] & Etienne Ruppé (INSERM) & Christophe Blanchet [IFB-core] & Nadia Goué [IFB; AuBi]</i></p>

WP2 Deliverables

		Delivery month
D2.1	Data Management Plan in its dynamic evolution (maDMP)	4

D2.2	Report on the results of the benchmarking of existing tools (available on the ABRomics-PF portal)	6
D2.3	Report on the benchmarking of existing relevant ontologies and “gap analysis”	10
D2.4	Workflow for genomic data preprocessing and quality control	12
D2.5	Workflow for genomic taxonomy classification including contamination detection	12
D2.6	Workflows for genomic de novo and reference-guided assemblies (short reads, long reads and hybrid) and quantity controls	12
D2.7	Workflow for metagenomic data preprocessing (including human reads removal) and quality control	12
D2.8	Knowledge base of antibiotic resistance genes first release	18
D2.9	ABRomics data warehouse first release	18
D2.10	Catalogue of semantic queries addressing geo and time-dependant questions of WP4 use-cases and WP3 modeling approaches	20
D2.11	Workflows for data annotation including the detection of genes and SNPs associated to AMR and virulence	24
D2.12	Workflows for genome-based typing (i.e., MLST, cgMLST), serotyping and phylogroup prediction, and cluster identification	24
D2.13	Workflows for plasmid detection (replication origin) and their typing (e.g. pMLST, relaxase-T4SS, pTU, MOB-suite)	24
D2.14	Workflow for identification and quantification of antibiotic resistance genes in metagenomic data (reads and contigs).	24
D2.15	Integrated semantic dataset leveraging the existing standards and ontologies and operationalizing FAIR principles	27
D2.16	Workflows for real-time tracking of AMR bacteria showing their spread in time and space (e.g. Nextstrain)	36
D2.17	Workflow for RNAseq experiments	48
D2.18	Workflow for the simulation of proteomes	48

WP3. Mathematical and bioinformatics tool development (obj 3)

Co-coordination

- Samuel Chaffron (CR CNRS, LS2N UMR6004 / IFB-BIRD)
- Benoit Doublet (DR INRAe; UMR1282, Infectiologie Santé Publique)
- Lulla Opatowski (PR, Group leader at Institut Pasteur, EMEA unit)
- François Sabot (DR IRD, Open Science Department Deputy Director)

Objectives

The overall objective of the WP3 is to **provide new mathematical and bioinformatics tools** dedicated to (i) ABR multi-omics data integration, (ii) decipher mechanisms of ABR transmission from genes to (pan)genomes, and inter-ecosystems levels, and (iii) the modelling of ABR emergence, selection and spread. This WP will aim to address generic needs in terms of bioinformatics analyses and models, relying on the WP1 computing architecture and the WP2 curated data. WP3 will provide access to state-of-the-art tools to detect, predict and model ABR genes from multi-omics data. Novel dedicated methods, models and workflows will also be developed and implemented to address shared goals associated with specific use-cases (WP4), while addressing yet unanswered needs of the ABRomics multi-omics platform users.

Description

The WP3, Mathematics and Bioinformatics tool development, **will establish the necessary bridge between the foundational WP1 and WP2, and research-oriented WP4 use-cases addressing overarching ABR questions (Fig5)**. WP3 members will design and build dedicated methodologies and softwares to answer these questions through specific developments and initial visualisations. The methodological and tools development will transversally benefit the AbROmics consortium through the different use-cases in WP4, as well as broadly serve the ABR research community.

The main transversal developments will include:

- Statistical and machine learning-based approaches for multi-omics data integration
- The detection of ABR gene variants and mobile genetic elements to track their dissemination
- The pan-genome-based identification and analysis of intra- and inter-species ABR transmission
- The eco-evolutionary modeling of ABR transmission and spread from pan-genomes across ecosystems
- The theoretical and data-driven dynamic modeling of ABR transmission and spread

Figure 3. The ABRomics platform WP3 ‘Mathematical and bioinformatics tool development’ overall structure and its interconnections with WP2 and WP4 use-cases.

Anticipating the generation of multi-omics datasets (e.g., proteomics, lipidomics, metabolomics) to study ABR, we will implement dedicated **machine learning techniques** (Drouin, 2016, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12864-016-2889-6>) for refining and predicting the antibiotic susceptibility and molecular phenotyping of specific antibiotic resistant strains of interest (e.g. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*) from multi-omics data (T3.1.1). These developments will be particularly useful to further characterize, via other omics (T3.1.2), bacterial strains that will be integrated within the ABRomics multi-omics integrated database (WP2). These integrated data (e.g., full genomes, SNPs, MGE presence) will also be associated with workflows for predicting ABR and for ABR biomarkers discovery, as well as for training new ABR prediction models (T3.1.1). Given the generation of multi-omics data within several WP4 use-cases (e.g., Pulmonary infections and Water) for host-associated and environmental microbiomes, we will also develop methods, and implement an associated workflow (Zoppi, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-020-03921-8>) relying on a **graph-based integration scheme for linking omics layers** across biological systems and traits (T3.1.3).

Investigating the intrinsic, acquired/mobile resistances within and between complex ecosystems considering humans, animal microbiomes but also the environment is crucial to understand the dynamics of ABR transmission and spread. We will develop a set of complementary methods and innovative analytical tools to determine the genetic context of ABR genes in (meta)genomic data. In strong interaction with the use-case Meta-PanGenomics, we will develop an **innovative approach to mine microbiome metagenomic data using pan-genome graph structures** combining the genomic content of all microbial strains for a species of interest. Pan-genome graphs (Gautreau, 2020, <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007732>) are particularly useful to discriminate between core and

accessory elements, the latter being particularly relevant to study ABR. We will develop workflows for directly mapping metagenomic reads on species pan-genome graphs to highlight relevant regions containing ABR and/or virulence factors and estimate relative abundances of specific variable genomic regions (T.3.2.1). Here, pan-genome graphs will be very useful to maintain an up-to-date strain-resolved genomic resource by systematically aggregating new genomes provided by WP2.

Besides, to further characterise ABR, we will implement a workflow to identify and track ABR gene variants in metagenomic datasets via a Bayesian approach based on SNP frequencies (T.3.2.2) (Quince, 2017, <http://doi.org/10.1186/s13059-017-1309-9>). As the mobility status of ABR genes is directly related to their surrounding genomic context (intrinsic/acquired, transposable, horizontally-mobile), we will also develop a bioinformatic workflow to predict the mobility status through in-depth analysis of ABR genes genetic context (MGE reference databases, proximity of mobility functions vs core-genomes) (T3.2.3) (Partridge, 2018, <http://doi.org/10.1128/CMR.00088-17>). This **genomic and genetic contextualization of ABR genes** will bring important information to the ABRomics knowledge-enriched database (WP2).

Conjugative elements, i.e. plasmids and integrative elements being key actors in Horizontal Gene Transfer (HGT) of ABR genes, we will develop a **dedicated analysis workflow for the detection of ABR plasmids and ABR integrated conjugative elements**. This workflow will rely on specialized softwares and will be applied to datasets of WP4 use-cases to compare the genomic environment of ABR in (meta)genomic data from various ecosystems (T3.2.3) (Redondo-Salvo, 2020, <http://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-17278>). Using the above information at both species and strain levels, we will project these variations at the ecosystem level, thereby detecting how ABR genes may spread across biological systems.

These developments will be instrumental to identify the current ABR state of ecosystems of interest, but also potential interactions between co-occurring pan-genomes and associated ABR genes. To reveal these ecological associations, we will implement algorithms (Kurtz, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004226>) to infer **pan-genome-resolved networks** to investigate potential spread of ABR genes within and across ecosystems (T3.2.4). To complement these ecological models, we will also implement tools to predict recent HGT informed by ABR gene variants detection (T.3.2.2.). Finally, these discrete eco-evolutionary models of ABR will be investigated through pan-genome niche modeling to link ABR to relevant environmental data (e.g. waterflow, temperature, nutrients concentration), detect (a)biotic factors related to ABR exposition and emergence, and to predict and inform potential ABR spread across reservoirs and ecosystems (T3.2.5).

To characterize and better understand the dynamics of ARG expansion within individuals (e.g., use-case Pulmonary infections), we will combine metagenome-based detection of ABR genes (WP2) with **time series data analysis and statistical models**. We will implement general approaches for spatio-temporal modelling (Meyer, 2017, <http://dx.doi.org/10.18637/jss.v077.i11>) of longitudinal data (T3.3.1): longitudinal differential abundance testing, temporal network inference, and temporal pattern clustering. The integration of longitudinal and cross-ecosystems (gut and lung) multi-omics data (T3.1.3) will inform us about how ABR evolution may lead to changes in host response and adaptation (use-case Pulmonary infections). Leveraging information from pan-genomic analyses (T3.2), the ABR evolution of niche-specific pathogens (e.g. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) will also be modelled.

A similar approach to study ABR evolution will be implemented at the epidemiological level through the development of a R package for the spatio-temporal statistical modeling of ABR genes and pathogens (T3.3.2). The models will include information integrated in the ABRomics database (WP2), such as specificity of the antibiotics, ABR genes, host, or location, and will also give the possibility to include contextual abiotic variables. These models may also integrate information from eco-systems models generated above (T3.2.4) (Jenness, 2018, <https://dx.doi.org/10.18637/jss.v084.i08>). **Mechanistic hypothesis-driven epidemiological transmission models** and their combination with statistical inference

can help analyse mechanisms of ABR genes transmission within and between populations. A critical limit is that integration of the genetic information is generally inexistent or very poor in these models. Here, we will develop a new mathematical modeling framework of ABR transmission between hosts (or reservoirs) by integrating genomic, genetic (use-case Pangenomics) and epidemiological data (use-case Pulmonary infections). These models will be combined with statistical inference techniques (e.g. Bayesian inference) to estimate model parameters, and confronted to longitudinal data.

All software developed in WP3 will be bundled using state-of-the-art package management and environment management systems (Conda, Singularity, Docker), which will facilitate their integration in the ABRomics-PF computing infrastructure (WP1) and their application by the ABRomics-PF users (WP2).

WP3 Tasks

Task	Task title	Task description	Person(s) involved [team]
T3.2.1	Pan-genome-based analysis to study intra- and inter-species ABR transmission (intrinsic resistances vs acquired resistances (mutations & mobile resistance genes))	See Use case 3 for details description	<i>Nicolas Pons [INRAE; MGP] & David Vallenet [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Benoît Doublet [INRAE] & Hélène Chiapello [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] & Valentin Loux [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] & CDD WP3.2 (30PM) 75% [ABRomics]</i>
T3.2.2	Detection of ABR gene variants in metagenomic data based on SNP frequencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - map metagenomic reads on ABR gene reference and extract SNPs. This step will be done using already existing SNP-calling tools such as Samtools. - develop a Bayesian approach to link SNPs into haplotypes/variants. The method will compare SNP frequencies and co-occurrences within and among samples to infer SNPs which belong to the same variant, in the spirit of the DESMAN/Constrains algorithm. - measure the prevalence and frequency of the detected variants among a set of metagenomic samples. 	<i>Benoît Doublet [INRAE] & Sébastien Leclercq [INRAE] & Nicolas Pons [INRAE; MGP] & David Vallenet [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Hélène Chiapello [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] & Valentin Loux [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] Patrick Plésiat & Katy Jeannot [CNR-RA] 3PM</i>

T3.2. 3	ABR mobile genetic elements analysis to track their dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - implementation of an analysis workflow for complete sequences of ABR plasmids based on already existing specialized tools (annotation, typing, comparative genomics and phylogenies of plasmid families/species) - provide an integrated data visualization for plasmid analysis (to be transmitted to WP6) - development of a bioinformatic workflow to analyse the surrounding genetic environment of ABR genes and to determine their mobility status (intrinsic/acquired, transposable, horizontally-mobile...) 	<p><i>Hélène Chiapello [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] & Valentin Loux [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] & Nicolas Pons [INRAE; MGP] & David Vallenet [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Benoît Doublet [INRAE] & Sébastien Leclercq [INRAE] & CDD WP3.3 (30PM) 25% [ABRomics]</i></p>
T3.1. 1	Machine-learning techniques for ABR prediction and biomarkers discovery (pathogen- and host-pathogen systems)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of novel machine learning-based methods for ABR prediction and biomarkers discovery - Implementation of a workflow to integrate genomics and metabolic data for fine-grained prediction of minimal inhibitory concentration - Validation of the machine learning models for ABR prediction 	<p><i>Laurent Jacob [IFB; LBBE] & Alexis Groppi [IFB; CBiB] & Bogdan Iorga [ICSN-CNRS]</i></p>
T3.1. 3	Graph-based approaches to integrate host-pathogen multi-omics data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of dedicated algorithms to infer omics-layer specific (temporal) networks - Development of statistical approaches to link omics layers across biological systems and traits or states - Statistical modeling to infer multi-omics signatures and biomarkers associated to ABR - Development of a R workflow integrating these techniques 	<p><i>Audrey Bihouée [IFB; BiRD PF] & Samuel Chaffron [IFB; BiRD PF] & Lourdes Velasco-Suárez [INSERM] & Antoine Roquilly [IFB; CHU Nantes] & CDD WP3.2 (18PM) & Pierre Larmande [IRD, IFB]</i></p>

T3.1. 2	Proteomics and proteogenomics insights into ABR and virulence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of an algorithm for integrating genomics and proteomics datasets, and modifying genome annotation with experimental peptide information, and prediction of proteotypic peptides for targeted proteomics measurements - Proposal of models (eventually genera- or species-specific) of expression/detectability of antibiotic resistance proteins and virulence factors - Validation of the model on novel experimental isolates with label-free proteomics datasets interpreted through ABRomics pan-genomic database 	<p><i>Jean Armengaud [CEA] & Christophe Junot [CEA], Francois Vandenesch (CNR et UCBL, 1 PM), Jérôme Lemoine (UCBL, 1PM) & CDD WP3.1 (12pm)</i></p>
T.3.2. 4	Intra- and inter-ecosystem networks inference to investigate eco-evo dynamics of ABR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of algorithms to infer (pan)genome-resolved networks - Detection of recent (ABR) gene flows on (pan)genome networks - Development of a workflow for the inference and analysis of eco-evo networks focusing on ABR 	<p><i>Samuel Chaffron [IFB; BiRD PF] & Audrey Bihouée [IFB; BiRD PF] & Francois Sabot [IFB; IRD] & Nicolas Pons [INRAE; MGP] & Florian Plaza-Onate [INRAE; MGP], Emmanuelle Le Chatelier [INRAE; MGP] & Mathieu Almeida [INRAE; MGP] & Guillaume Gautreau [INRAE; MGP] & David Vallenet [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Benoît Doublet [INRAE] & Hélène Chiapello [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] & CDD WP3.4 (12PM) & Pierre Larmande [IRD,IFB]</i></p>
T.3.2. 5	Species niche modeling to model and predict ABR spread and detect (a)biotic factors of ABR exposition, emergence and spread	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of methods for species/strain (genome) niche modeling - Development of a workflow for analysing (pan)genome networks and predict potential ABR spread across reservoirs/ecosystems 	<p><i>Samuel Chaffron [IFB; BiRD PF] & Audrey Bihouée [IFB; BiRD PF] & Francois Sabot [IFB; IRD] & Nicolas Pons [INRAE; MGP] & David Vallenet [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Benoît Doublet [INRAE] & Hélène Chiapello [INRAE; IFB Migale PF] & CDD WP3.4 (12PM)</i></p>

T3.3.1	Spatio-temporal modeling and analysis of epidemiological data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of statistical model to analyze the spatio temporal trends of ABR exploiting the epidemiological data over time. The model will include information available in the database such as specificity of the antibiotics, resistance genes, host, location etc and may also give the possibility to include external variables such as climatic variables - Building a R package to analyze spatio-temporal time series of ABR in different reservoirs - Building a R shiny interface to make the analysis exploitable quickly and easily by non expert users 	<p><i>Lourdes Velo-Suárez [INSERM] & Lulla Opatowski [Pasteur] & Geneviève Héry-Arnaud [INSERM] & CDD WP3.5 (12PM)</i></p>
T3.3.2	Development of epidemiological models and combination with statistical inference to analyze ABR transmission from epidemiological data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of mathematical model of ABR transmission between hosts by integrating the genetic and epidemiological data - Development of mathematical model of ABR transmission between reservoirs - Use of statistical inference techniques to estimate model parameters and confront models to data collected over time - Building a R package that embed the different techniques 	<p><i>Lulla Opatowski [Pasteur] & Lourdes Velo-Suárez [INSERM] & Geneviève Héry-Arnaud [INSERM] & CDD WP3.5 (12PM)</i></p>

WP3 Deliverables

		Delivery month
D3.1	Programmatic and graphical interface dedicated to ABR plasmids study in genomic/metagenomic data	24
D3.2	R code and workflow for graph-based dimensionality reduction for multi-omics ABR data exploration and integration	24
D3.3	A python algorithm for exploiting proteogenomic data for improving the annotation of genomes	30
D3.4	Workflows for ABR biomarkers discovery, for predicting ABR from data deposited in the platform (e.g. full genomes, SNPs, MGE presence) and for training new prediction models from data deposited in the platform (if available trained models are unsuitable). Novel GWAS and/or prediction methods if existing approaches are not enough to address use cases.	36
D3.5	Visualization of multi-omics associations and multi-omics biomarkers associated to ABR	36
D3.6	A workflow for analysis of ABR genes variants and their tracking in metagenomic datasets provided as both a programmatic and graphical interface	36
D3.7	Workflow for genetic environment contextualization of ABR genes and addition of this information in reference databases of WP2	36
D3.8	Workflow for the inference and analysis of (pan)genome-resolved networks within and across ecosystems	36
D3.9	R & python modules for species niche modeling and prediction of ABR transmission and spread potential across ecosystems	36
D3.10	Workflow for Pan-genome-based analysis to study intra- and inter-species ABR transmission	48
D3.11	Proteomics datasets for 120 strains	48
D3.12	Workflow for the detection of recent gene flows on (pan)genome-resolved networks	48
D3.13	Visualization and analysis of ABR transmission and spread potential across ecosystems	48
D3.14	R package for modelling ABR transmission including genetic and epidemiological data in populations and between epidemiological reservoirs	48
D3.15	R package/shiny for temporal statistical analysis of ABR epidemiological data	48

WP3 GANTT chart

WP4. Transversal use cases

Co-coordination:

- Christophe Junot (Head of department/unit. CEA, Paris Saclay, Deputy director of MetaboHUB, French National Infrastructure in Metabolomics and Fluxomics)
- Geneviève Hery-Arnaud (Centre Brestois d'Analyse du Microbiote (CBAM), INSERM)
- Nicolas Pons (Bioinformatics Group leader, team InfoBioStat, MetaGenoPolis, INRAe)
- Patrick Plésiat (NRC Antibiotic Resistance (Besançon), Bacteriology)

Objectives

The adoption of the ABRomics-PF computing resources by the communities of epidemiologists, clinical microbiologists from the human and animal sectors, microbiologist of the environment and the broader research community will be piloted by six use cases that will address specific objectives related to the investigation of hospital or veterinary clinic outbreaks, and the analysis of antimicrobial resistance in a One Health framework considering also the environment using genomic, metagenomics and other omics data.

Importantly, these implementation studies will contribute to drive the technological choices of the 3 work packages, and provide realistic study cases to evaluate the relevance of the infrastructure to address the actual needs of user communities. They will lead to Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for future users describing the way ABRomics-PF should be operated to address the question underpinning each use case.

Description

The use cases have been selected to cover a diverse range of questions and challenges in ABR surveillance and research in a One Health context. The selected use cases generally rely on ongoing or submitted scientific projects to other calls (H2020, PPR antibiotic resistance, etc.; cf. **Appendix 6.3**), meaning that the production of experimental data, some developments and bioanalysis tasks are already funded. Indeed, these six use cases will lead to new tools and pipelines developments (in collaboration with WP2, WP3 and WP6 for visualization purposes), tested on the use case data set(s).

A detailed description of each use case is provided in **Appendix 3**, with a definition of the objective, outlines, tasks and deliverables.

We provide hereafter a short description of each use case:

Use Case 1 (UC1): Detection and investigation of outbreak involving multidrug resistant bacteria

UC1 aims to demonstrate the contribution of the ABRomics platform in the investigation of hospital or veterinary clinic outbreaks and possible environmental sources involving multidrug resistant (MDR) Gram-negative pathogens. The roadmap from data input to outputs for this use case is depicted in Figure 1.

Use Case 2 (UC2): One Health approach to the emergence, transition and dissemination of antimicrobial resistance in *Acinetobacter baumannii*

UC2 aims to demonstrate the contribution of the ABRomics platform in the analysis of antimicrobial resistance in a One Health framework. Specifically, the project will require to store a large set of A.

baumannii (Ab) genomes sampled from different environments, along with their metadata and to perform a joint statistical and ecological analysis of these samples.

Use Case 3 (UC3): Application of Meta-PanGenomic concept for tracking antibioresistance in metagenomic samples

UC3 aims to demonstrate the potential application of Meta-PanGenomic concept for tracking associations at the species and strain levels between antimicrobial resistance and pathogenicity in the context of human microbiota but could also be applied to any complex microbial ecosystem.

Use Case 4 (UC4): Pulmonary infections

UC4 aims to demonstrate the contribution of the ABRomics platform in the analysis of antimicrobial resistance in pulmonary infections. Two types of lung infections corresponding to two different clinical and ecological contexts will be addressed: (i) chronic lung infections that require repeated and long-lasting antibiotic courses, and (ii) acute lung infections, which are infections with a vital prognosis in the short term and which require rapidly effective antibiotic cures (short-lasting antibiotic courses, mostly intravenously).

Use Case 5 (UC5): One Health dissemination of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) through aquatic environments (continental, oceanic and waste water)

UC5 aims to explore the role of different aquatic environments (waste water, continental and oceanic) in the dissemination of the antimicrobial resistance (AMR) thanks to the contribution of the ABRomics platform.

Use Case 6 (UC6): Proteomics for antibiotic susceptibility testing and molecular phenotyping of antibiotic resistant bacterial strains

UC6 aims to demonstrate how the ABRomics-PF can be used to combine genomic data with high-resolution targeted proteomics in order to identify isolates and their expressed antibiotic resistances. Two complementary tasks will be undertaken from data stored in the ABRomics database: (i) automated exploitation of gene sequencing data for the design of targeted and quantitative proteomic methods for antibiotic susceptibility testing, and (ii) proteogenomics insights into antibiotic gene resistance and virulence.

WP4 Tasks

Task	Task title	Task description	Person(s) involved [team]
T4.1	Development, benchmark and validation of Meta-PanGenome graph method	Development of Meta-PanGenome graph method including graph construction, read mapping, deconvolution method and visualization. Benchmark and validation on human gut metagenomic data Support WP3, WP6.	<i>Nicolas Pons [INRAE; MGP] & David Vallenet [IFB; MicroScope PF] & Florian Plaza-Onãte [INRAE; MGP], Emmanuelle Le Chatelier [INRAE; MGP] & Mathieu Almeida [INRAE; MGP] & Guillaume Gautreau [INRAE; MGP] & Claudine Médigue [IFB; MicroScope PF]</i>
T4.6	Proteomic analysis of 120 reference antibiotic resistant strains	Submission of high-quality, top-annotated experimental label-free proteome datasets for 120 referenced strains to the ABRomics database with their antibiotics susceptibility extensive characterization. Support WP2	<i>Jean Armengaud [CEA] & Christophe Junot [CEA]</i>
T4.2	Analysis of the spatio-temporal dissemination of epidemic multidrug resistant strains	Generate spatio-temporal views (i.e., nextstrain) of data selected by the user among sequences types, core genome clusters, resistances mechanisms, virulence genes, AST data and metadata	<i>Richard Bonnet [CNR-RA] & Vincent Cattoir [CNR-RA] & Patrick Plésiat & Katy Jeannot 12PM</i>
T4.5	Deciphering of ABR dissemination across aquatic environments in a One Health context	See use case 5 for description	<i>Anne-Laure Bañuls, MIVEGEC-IRD, Christian Lienhardt, TransVIHMI-IRD, Benoit Doublet [INRAE, PGBA], Mallorie Hide, MIVEGEC-IRD, Sylvain Godreuil, Bacteriology laboratory CHU Arnaud de Villeneuve/MIVEGEC-IRD, Patrick Durand, MIVEGEC-IRD, Marion Vittecoq, Tour du Valat/MIVEGEC-IRD, Patricia Licznar, HSM-IRD, Estelle Bilak, HSM-IRD, Fabien Aujoulat, HSM-IRD, François Sabot, MSO-IRD, Jean Christophe Auguet, MARBEC-IRD, Thierry Bouvier, MARBEC-IRD, Marine Combes, ISEM-IRD, Samira Serter, ISEM-IRD, Rudy Gonzlan, ISEM-IRD, Marie-Cécile Ploy, RESINFIT-INSERM, Philippe Glaser, EERA-Institut Pasteur & Sebastien Leclercq [INRAE, PGBA] & Pierre Larmande [IRD, IFB]</i>

T4.3	Understanding the main drivers of ABR in <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	Identify the main drivers of ABR in <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> by combining information gathered on the relationship between the environment and bacterial species, selective pressures and mechanisms of acquisition/transfer.	
T4.4	Characterization of the ARGs expansion within the lung ecosystem	Development of applications to integrate both WGS and metagenomics data collected at different time-points and under different antimicrobial treatment courses - Support: WP3	<i>Antoine Roquilly [IFB; CHU Nantes] & Jeremie Poshman [IFB; INSERM] & Geneviève Héry-Arnaud [INSERM] & Lourdes Velo-Suárez [INSERM] & Samuel Chaffron [IFB; BiRD PF] & Audrey Bihouée [IFB; BiRD PF] & Olivier Barraud [CHU; RESINFIT]</i>

WP4 Deliverables

			Delivery month
WP4	D4.1	Guidelines and reproducible workflows to decipher the spatio-temporal dissemination of epidemic multidrug-resistant bacteria	48
WP4	D4.2	A blueprint describing the analysis of genomic and metagenomic data gathered over a gradient of anthropized environments to anticipate and control the spread of ABR in a One Health perspective.	48
WP4	D4.3	Guidelines and reproducible workflows for applying Meta-PanGenomic approach in ABROmics-PF	48
WP4	D4.4	ARGs expansion in the lung under antimicrobial selection pressure	48
WP4	D4.5	Guidelines for targeted and/or shotgun multi-omic integration and application to ABR dissemination within and between aquatic ecosystems	48
WP4	D4.6	Predicting of proteotypic peptides for detectability of antibiotic resistance proteins and virulence factors.	48
WP4	D4.7	A Standard Operating Procedure for proteomics datasets submission and proteogenomics interpretation.	48

WP5. Community engagement, training and outreach

Co-coordination

1. Thierry Naas (PI NRC EPC, Hôpital Bicêtre, Paris)
2. Claudine Médigue (DR CNRS; co director of the French Bioinformatics Institute)
3. Jacques van Helden (PR AMU; co director of the French Bioinformatics Institute)
4. Hélène Chiapello (CR INRAe; co leader of the training activities in IFB and French representative in the ELIXIR training platform)

Objectives

This work package will develop actions to foster the engagement of the contributing communities, and to ensure the reachout to the different communities targeted by the project.

This will include various actions

1. Scientific communication (publications, conferences)
2. Developing training material and training events for the end-users
3. Organising hackathons to engage the communities in the adoption and improvement of the ABRomics platform
4. Communication towards non-specialist audiences
5. Develop partnerships with industry

Description

Scientific communication should primarily target the communities of microbiologists (European Congress of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases (**ECCMID**), American Society of Microbiology Microbe meeting (**ASM Microbe**), Réunion interdisciplinaire de chimio-thérapie anti-infectieuse (**RICAI**) and Journées Nationales d'Infectiologie (**JNI**), but also reach the bioinformatics communities (*i.e.*, JOBIM, ELIXIR all-hands, ISMB, ECCB), in order to emphasize the potential re-use of the platform's architecture and tools to address other applications of multi-omics integration.

Training material will rely on a combination of static material (user manuals for all the tools of the platform, online tutorials based on relevant use cases), dynamic material (video courses and demos) and interactive training events (webinars, on-site training workshops, hackathons). Training events will be organised to bring together the different communities involved in the development and the use of the platform. In a first phase, hackathons will gather the developers and selected beta-testers, in order to perform realistic tests of the platform based on actual datasets produced by the microbiologists (Bring Your Own Data). Expected outcomes are feedback and suggestions to enhance the user-friendliness and the adequation of the interfaces with the end-users needs and of new pipelines to implement. Following this optimisation, we will organise at least one "curatathons", *i.e.* a short event (2-3 days) bringing together specialists of resistance databases in order to curate and check the consistency and relevance of the annotations and perform a time-intensive collective curation effort.

The ABRomics-PF communities engagement and training actions will also be developed in synergy with WP3 of the PROMISE project (call "Professional Meta-network of the PPR antibioresistance), which will carried out connected actions: (i) animation of the network of actors and the provision of information, (ii)

development of resources for communication and awareness raising, and (iii) development of degree courses and taking these issues into account in existing courses.

In addition to the Web portal dedicated to the scientific and clinicians users (defined in WP6), we will implement user-friendly web pages targeting a public of non-specialists (press, patient associations, stakeholders, general public, policy makers) in order to account for the good use of the public funding by providing a clear and synthetic view on the goals and achievements of the project.

The activities should ensure that our research activities are made known to society at large in such a way that they can be understood by non-specialists, thereby improving the public's understanding of science. Direct engagement with the public will help researchers to better understand public interest in priorities for science and technology and also the public's concerns. Society could appreciate the responsibilities and the motivation that researchers demonstrate in executing their work at different stages of their careers and in their multifaceted role. These activities will be build on Scientific blog, e-Newsletters, Wikipedia, eBrochures, eEvents such as public talks, workshops day for school/university students, "Café Scientifique" (forum for debating science issues, dedicated to large public) such as: Conférence Cyclope, CEA Orsay)

Finally, different industries and private laboratories are expected to be also users of the ABRomics-PF, for example in the context of collaborations with public laboratories. The scientific communication and public outreach will aim to provide and facilitate interaction with the private sector.

WP5 Tasks

Task	Task title	Task description	Person(s) involved [team]
T5.1	Support for scientific communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - specifications for communication support and the ABRomics graphic charter - definition of the Web pages content for specialists and non specialists (WP6) - Scientific blog, Newsletters, Wikipedia, eBrochures etc. 	<i>Claudine Médigue [IFB, MicroScope] & Suzanne Lauriou [IFB-core] & Thierry Naas [CNR] & CDD 75% [ABRomics] & Angela Saenz [IFB-core]</i>
T5.2	Trainings on the ABRomics-PF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - preparation of trainings materials - organisation of trainings on the resources available in the ABRomics-PF - organisation of hackathon(s) (link with use cases proposed in WP4) 	<i>Jacques van Helden [IFB; ATGC PF] & Olivier Sand [IFB-core] & Benoit Doublet [INRAE, PGBA] & Sebastien Leclercq [INRAE, PGBA] & Marion Vittecoq [IRD, MIVEGEC] & Hélène Chiapello [IFB, MIGALE PF]</i>
T5.3	Organisation of communication events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - workshop day for school/university students - eEvents such as public talks - forum dedicated to large public 	<i>Hélène Chiapello [IFB, MIGALE PF] & Olivier Barraud [CHU, RESINFIT] & Geneviève Hery Arnaud [CHU, CBAM, INSERM] & François Sabot [IRD, MSO] & Suzanne Lauriou [IFB-core] & Angela Saenz [IFB-core]</i>

WP6. Web portal

Co-coordination:

- Claudine Médigue (co director of the French Bioinformatics Institute)
- Sylvain Milanesi (IFB developer : help-desk and IFB web site)
- Suzanne Lauriou (communication manager, IFB)

Objectives

Development of a common **open access, privacy-preserving Web portal**, transversal to the three technical components of the platform (WP1, WP2 and WP3), the various use cases proposed in WP4, the management and coordination of the project (WP0), and the training and outreach (WP5) activities of the ABRomics-PF.

Description

Dedicated to any kind of users, this portal will allow to:

- manage users access and rights (**administration entry point**),
- upload user data and metadata into the shared or private data spaces (**submission entry point**),
- launch analysis tools and pipelines (**analysis entry point**),
- curate reference strains and genes/variants (**curation entry point**),
- visualize data and metadata (analysis results & search results) in user-friendly interfaces (**visualization entry point**),
- browse, search and suggest modifications/extensions to the community agreed controlled vocabularies, ontologies and other standards recommended for data curation (**standard specification entry point**),
- explore and access the data available in the integrated multi-omics database (**search and discovery entry point**),
- give a clear and synthetic view on the goals and achievements of the project through outreaching/impact web pages targeting a public of non-specialists (**outreach entry point**).
- list training events organized by the ABRomics-PF consortium in collaboration with the one of the PROMISE project (**training entry point**)

The general ABRomics-PF website will also refer to the Inserm portal on the Priority Program on Antibiotic resistance, <https://ppr-antibioresistance.inserm.fr>, and the Health Data Hub portal, <https://www.health-data-hub.fr/>.

WP6 Tasks

Task	Task title	Task description	Person(s) involved [team]
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T6.1	Drafting the specifications of the ABR-omics portal	Specifications for the <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - administration entry point - submission entry point - analysis entry point - curation entry point - visualization entry point - standards specification entry point - search and discovery entry point - outreach entry point - training entry point 	<i>Christophe Blanchet [IFB Core] & CDD WP1.2 [ABRomics] & CDD WP1.3 [tbd] & Claudine Médigue [IFB, MicroScope] & Suzanne Lauriou [IFB-core] & Sylvain Milanesi [IFB-Core] & Angela Saenz [IFB-core]</i>
T6.2	Development of the entries point for communication and trainings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interfaces for the professional and non professional users - interfaces for trainings 	<i>Claudine Médigue [IFB, MicroScope] & Suzanne Lauriou [IFB-core] & Sylvain Milanesi [IFB-Core]</i>
T6.3	Development of the entries point linked to WP1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interfaces to manage users access and rights, and data submission - Interfaces to interact with the private bioprojects: findability, edition, analysis management with traceability of actions - creation of datasets and export procedure 	<i>CDD WP1.2 [ABRomics] & CDD WP1.3 [ABRomics] & Christophe Blanchet [IFB Core] & Sylvain Milanesi [IFB-Core]</i>
T6.4	Development of the entries point linked to WP2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interfaces to interact with data stored in the ABRomics database - Interfaces with external resources: findability, creation of datasets and import/export procedures - interfaces to launch standard analysis workflow - visualisation interfaces of results - interfaces for the data curation 	<i>Claudine Médigue [IFB, MicroScope] & Sylvain Milanesi [IFB-Core]</i>
T6.5	Development of the entries point linked to WP3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - interfaces to launch advanced analysis tools and pipelines - visualisation interfaces of results 	<i>Sylvain Milanesi [IFB-Core] & Rémi Planel [Pasteur]</i>

T6.6	Development of the entries point linked to WP4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - formalization of the use-case needs - backend system to glob, format and in-memory load data to be visualised - dedicated visualisation panels for two beta test use-cases. - Visualization panel for all uses-cases 	<i>Claudine Médigue [IFB, MicroScope] & Sylvain Milanesi [IFB-Core]</i>
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WP6 Deliverables

		Delivery month
D6.1	Design of the ABRomics web site (empty shell)	6
D6.2	Beta version of the Web portal (internal use and testing)	12
D6.3	First release of the Web portal	14
D6.4	Second release of the Web portal	24
D6.5	Final release of the Web portal	36

WP6 GANTT chart

3.4 Expected impact (Opportunities)

The genomic sequences of bacterial pathogens and other omics data related to antibiotic resistance represent opportunities for clinical research and public health. The ABRomics platform will fill the existing gap on the integration of hardware, software, data and resources by providing technical means and expertises for this organisation and analysis of the data across sectors. It aims to have an impact on the use of WGS and omics data for any researcher working in the field of AMR, from clinicians and field investigators to fundamental researchers and modelers. ABRomics-PF will provide automated and validated pipelines for simple analysis of genomic and metagenomic data, as well as the access to sophisticated tools.

Added-value of the ABRomics-PF in the short, medium and long-terms

In the short term the ABRomics-PF project will provide a user-friendly platform to store, share, submit data sequences and their annotation to international repositories, and analyze data with the most efficient and validated tools and workflows. In the longer term, ABRomics-PF will ensure the broadest possible preservation of genomics and other omics data for retrospective studies.

Importantly ABRomics-PF will provide a common language (bacterial WGS) to federate clinicians and researchers from the human, animal and environmental sector, linking the key players in the field of antibiotic resistance with those contributing to infrastructure and bioinformatics resources.

While user-friendly bioinformatic analysis platforms are available, the different public health environments, data sharing policies and computer infrastructures, hamper their usage. ABRomics-PF is conceived as a public health solution to securely integrate cross-jurisdictional high-throughput sequencing data, phenotypic and epidemiological information within a harmonized, standard-compliant, flexible communication platform. By reducing the technical burden of handling high-throughput and AMR data, while preserving compliance with jurisdictional data protection policies, ABRomics-PF will provide an interface for effective data management and streamlined data analysis of samples derived from multiple sectors and projects. The large collection of customizable bioinformatics pipelines integrated into ABRomics-PF will enable users to perform standardized analysis of microbial sequencing data and combine them with relevant metadata to finally model the evolution of antibiotic resistance, the transmission and dissemination of clones and genes within and between sectors. This will support timely public health actions with data-driven criteria for the prioritization of surveillance efforts and promote retrospective studies and longitudinal surveillance in the framework of One Health and Global Health.

Improving the quality and workflow of bacterial genome sequencing and analysis will pave the way for a France-wide molecular epidemiological surveillance platform providing spatiotemporal approaches. If WGS data analysis can explain the spatiotemporal patterns of pathogen transmission, the transmission between compartments (human, animal, food, environment) remains however very complex. The interoperable and curated metadata stored in the ABRomics-PF database will be a key requirement for fully understanding this complexity and thereby will enable a One Health surveillance system for the transmission of data on MDR pathogens of different species and environments. Although mainly focusing on MDR pathogens, susceptible strains will also be included to give some background controls and to potentially investigate other aspects, such as specific gene transmission.

Human and veterinary microbiologists will therefore better understand transmission routes, which will pave the way to development of new prevention strategies at the most critical cross-points. Public health authorities would have a high-quality, nearly real-time surveillance tool for a detailed assessment and tracking of single pathogenic and/or multidrug-resistant strains but also large scale outbreaks. Hospital epidemiologists, infection control specialists and clinicians could connect outbreaks to potential sources inside and outside of hospitals. Regulatory agencies could link potential contaminated products to

improve patient safety. Researchers could access the database and use the available multi-omics data and tools to develop more complex transmission models, which go beyond automated surveillance.

General public awareness about transmission events between compartments will also be raised from the project through WP5. At last, due to the high interest of all involved institutions in such a platform, there is a very high potential to develop it into a sustainable tool for future epidemiological surveillance.

Integration of ABRomics-PF in the international context

The analytical workflow is still a major bottleneck, especially because best practices and pipelines are not available. The ABRomics project will offer the opportunity to define, in collaboration with international experts of the ELIXIR network (www.elixir-europe.org), standards for sequence quality control and subsequent bioinformatic analysis. Indeed, through our leading role in several ELIXIR communities of which Marine metagenomics and Microbial biotechnology, scientific communities associated to ABRomics will benefit from the impact of ELIXIR to the French node: (i) a powerful environment supporting the European contribution to the development of standards and generic tools for the community in life sciences, (ii) the support of co-development activities through internal projects between ELIXIR nodes, staff exchanges, but also through hackathons, (iii) the interactions with other ESFRIs (EMPHASIS, EMBRC, ECRIN, MIRRI, IBISBA) and the participation to EU-funded projects.

Several widely used species-specific and species-agnostic AMR databases and gene detection tools are currently available. However, these tools differ in terms of inputs, functionality (including parameters and reference databases), and outputs, which may present different structure and range of values. This challenges the comparison and interpretation of meaningful results for public health experts and researchers. To address these issues, the ABRomics-PF will implement a standardized AMR gene detection output specification, in line with the international project hAMRization <https://github.com/pha4ge/hAMRization>, to better harmonize the AMR detection results across tools and resources and improve interoperability. The pipeline will combine the outputs of disparate antimicrobial resistance gene detection tools into a single unified format for enabling comparisons and benchmarking of data as well as reporting of AMR resistance determinants between health agencies and laboratories.

With the implementation of a structured surveillance platform at national level, the international community will benefit by the sharing of evidence, experiences, and examples of good practice in AMR data management and modelling. The successful implementation of a national surveillance system through ABRomics-PF is a key element to facilitate cross-country learning and support collective action in addressing this global challenge.

3.5 Risks and foreseen solutions

ABRomics-PF is an ambitious project which aims to respond to the three objectives defined in the call for proposals. However, the maximum budget foreseen for this call is limited and this might represent a risk. We have limited this risk by taking advantage of the IFB's National Network Computing Resources (IFB NNCR). ABRomics-PF will also rely on the developments and computer equipment planned in the IFB's MuDIS4LS recently-accepted project. Therefore, the vast majority of the requested budget is dedicated to bioinformatics (and mathematical) developments through the recruitment of engineers.

To address the ambitious goals of the ABRomics-PF project, we have gathered a large consortium with teams sharing the needed expertises and competences. However, management of such a consortium, delocalized on the French territory, can represent a risk. Indeed, the organisation and management of the ABRomics-PF will take advantage of the present IFB organization (collaborative work performed in groups of persons gathered in "task forces") and of the on-going collaborations between partners. This clearly provides a coherence to our consortium. We will also set up a management organization in terms of committees and communication means, as well as tools to monitor the progress of the tasks for which the ABRomics-PF partners are responsible, in order to avoid any drift in the conduct of the project.

Another risk lies in the number and diversity of the tasks associated with the ABRomics-PF project, especially in WP2 and WP3. Careful consideration has been therefore given to structuring the project and gathering a broad diversity of skills within the consortium. In addition, a hierarchy of tasks has been defined in order to meet the priority needs expressed by the medical microbiologists, the reference centers and researchers involved in the consortium. Finally, we have defined a specific WP for the development of interfaces and data visualization to guarantee the user-friendliness of the ABRomics-PF.

WP3, the aim of which is to develop new tools for data analysis, data integration and mathematical modeling, is central to the ABRomics platform, interfacing the foundational WP1 and WP2, for serving WP4 use-cases. The resulting workflows might be complex and difficult to integrate into the ABRomics infrastructure developed in WP1 and for the development of the corresponding interface in WP6. To address this risk, we will foster continuous interactions between members of WP1, 2, 3 and 6 to develop best practices during workflow developments in order to homogenize and facilitate their integration in the WP1 platform and their use in WP2.

New Appendix : “IFB & ELIXIR”

The Institut **Français de Bioinformatique (IFB)** consists of 31 regional platforms of services (PFs) spanning the entire territory, belonging to the main French research organizations (see below), and a national hub, **called IFB-core**, located at Genoscope, Evry (since August 2018), which is a joint service unit depending on 5 supervisory authorities (CNRS, CEA, INRA, INSERM, INRIA). IFB-core is the French node for ELIXIR and has signed a Collaboration Agreement with the ELIXIR hub.

The 31 regional PFs provision services and technical support to scientific projects of their local life science community. They also provide training, develop code for the life science community and share a part of their IT infrastructure. Regional PFs are embedded in bioinformatics research laboratories and are thus able to preserve a critical link between provisions of service and research activities. They share their expertise in complementary fields: Agriculture and forestry (INRA platforms), Health (INSERM platforms), Microbiology (CNRS and CEA platforms, Institut Pasteur), Ecology (CNRS platforms), etc.

IFB-core (Figure 1), provides an administrative and technical support to IFB, implements the scientific and technological policy and ensures the dissemination of the actions, sets up and administers the IFB national IT facility, takes care of communication and outreach activities, coordinates technological and scientific activities (task forces, training, workshops, scientific meetings, etc.), and acts as the French representative entity for the French node of ELIXIR

Figure 1. Schematic representation of IFB structure. IFB-core is the national hub. Its direction interacts with the leaders of all the regional platforms, especially through the regular meetings which gathers all the heads of the IFB bioinformatics platforms (Cell of Interactions between regional Platforms and IFB-Core; CIPI). The platforms themselves are collaborating on biological applications, technological developments and training activities (colored lines between regional platforms).

The coordination of the actions relies on a **model of decentralisation** depicted in Figure 1: the national funding of the new IFB work plan enables IFB core to recruit temporary staff (mainly engineers in computer sciences or bioinformatics), each of which is affected to the regional platform most adequate for the realisation of her/his national missions (in terms of competences and/or co-ordination of the corresponding task/WP).

IFB has a fundamental role in **the mutualization of physical, logistics and human resources to address user's needs**, to promote technological developments, to **enforce technology and scientific watch at the national and European levels (via ELIXIR)**, to set-up training in line with the constant evolution of the domain, and to provide user support. The IFB work plan is organized around a **“mutualized task-force”** gathering various experts of different IFB platforms to optimize the sharing of knowledge and competences, the design of robust and innovative solutions, and to deploy IFB services.

IFB as the French node of ELIXIR = ELIXIR-FR

ELIXIR-FR is amongst the largest nodes of the European bioinformatics infrastructure, with a large panel of platforms, activities and services addressing a wide diversity of domains such as human health, food and agriculture, and marine diversity. Our activities encompass most of the ELIXIR platforms (compute, tools, training, interoperability). The development of our national registry of bioinformatics resources (compute & storage facilities, tools, training materials, expertise, teams) is synchronised with the corresponding ELIXIR registries (bio.tools, EDAM, TeSS) and standards (Bioschemas) in order to enable a **both-ways programmatic synchronisation between resources annotated in the French and ELIXIR repositories**.

IFB/ELIXIR-FR has set up a national group of people devoting a specific percentage of their time to interactions with ELIXIR-hub (via the 2 HoN + an 1 Deputy) as well as other ELIXIR nodes (participation to platforms and communities). ELIXIR-FR collaborates with other ELIXIR nodes in the context of several communities: Plants Sciences (co-lead), hCNV (lead), Galaxy (co-lead), Microbial Biotechnology (co-lead), Rare Diseases, Marine Metagenomics (co-lead), Proteomics, Metabolomics, Intrinsicly Disordered Proteins, and 3D-Bioinfo. Regarding the ELIXIR technological platforms, 1 French ExCo (PF Tools) has been nominated in 2020. The table below summarizes the involvement per ELIXIR activity (communities, platforms, coordination) for 2020-2022.

Category (1)	2020	2021	2022
Communities	1.35	1.35	1.05
Compute	0.35	0.35	0.35
Data	0.65	0.65	0.65
HoN	0.60	0.60	0.60
Interoperability	1.60	1.60	1.10
Management	1.00	1.00	1.00
Tools	1.10	1.15	1.15
Training	1.15	1.15	1.15
Grand Total	7.80	7.85	7.05

(1) This table includes the permanent staff involved in IFB WP coordination as well as the temporary personnel directly involved in actions related to ELIXIR priorities (e.g. interoperability, data management, ...).

Key indicators - IFB / ELIXIR-FR

Category	Indicator	2019	2020
Compute and storage services			
	Total number of active users	7 811	9 115
	New user accounts opened	3 566	2 911
	Active project spaces	7 670	6 886
	New project spaces opened	2 689	2 376
	Computing capacity (CPU)	NA	28 924
	GPU-based computing capacity	NA	234
	Usage rate of the computing capacity	NA	52,12%
	Storage capacity (Tb)	NA	29 019
	Average usage rate of the storage capacity	NA	60 %
Software development and deployment			
	New software tools developed	72	56
	Downloads of software tools	18 540	16 607
	Unique users for Web interfaces of IFB resources	302 143	423 424
	Unique users for API interfaces of IFB resources		1 029
Support actions to user projects			
	Total number of support actions	1 072	881
	- provision of services (with payment)	NA	571
	- collaborations	NA	310
	- Collaborations internal to the institute	233	161
	- Academic projects	570	169
	- at the national level	570	282

	- at international level	252	249
	- projects with international collaboration	NA	49
	- partnership with enterprise	24	27
	- involving private partners	24	23
Scientific collaborations			
	Total number of collaborative projects	NA	310
	Percent of satisfied or very satisfied collaborators	NA	98%
Training			
	Number of training events	138	127
	Total number of trained persons	2 169	2 326
	Percent of satisfied or very satisfied trainees	92.62%	94.40%
	Master and PhD supervision	NA	95
Human resources			
	IFB-funded temporary contracts	NA	21
	Permanent staff recruited	14	8
Outreach			
	Scientific events organised (events, conferences...)	33	55
	Publications	416	431
	Publications with IFB in affiliations	22	15
	Publications with IFB platform as first or last author	44	43
	Publications with IFB platform as intermediate author	237	212
	Total number of citations	8 894	11 217
	Oral communications	57	43
Economical indicators			
	Number of funded projects	NA	55
	- academic	44	50
	- with private partners	7	5
	Income from the projects (K€)	k€3,086.00	k€2,337.93
	- academic	k€1,472.99	k€1,679.64
	- private	k€514.00	k€658.29
	Number of platforms with active pricing system	15	14
	Income from pricing of services (K€)	k€532.00	k€715.00
	Number of patents deposited	1	2

New Appendix : Genomics and Metagenomics (meta)Data in ABROmic

A) File storage and management system for genomic data and metadata

1. Data type (formats, size, number)

- Sample metadata

In order to represent the metadata, we will define a data type designated “metadata”. Metadata will be treated as data objects within the system. They will support data submission, access services and compatibility with international databases. The requirements for each sample are reported in table 1. Each metadata will be associated to Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST) and omics data.

Table 1: Requirements for each sample provided

FEATURES		MANDATORY
Sample		
sample_id	Sample ID (same as metadat ID)	Yes
sample_type	human; animal; environmental; food, other	Yes
sample_source	description of the site of isolation	No
sample_zip	ZIP code where the sample was performed	No
sample_country	country where the sample was isolated	Yes
sample_coordinates	latitude, longitude	No
sample_date	date of isolation	Yes
sample_storage	Indicate if the isolate is stored, how and for how long	Yes
sample_laboratory_ID	unique ID of the laboratory processing the sample	No
Microbio data		
species_type	Bacteria; fungi; virus	Yes
species_name	NCBI taxonomy name for microorganism	Yes
taxonomy_ID	NCBI taxonomy ID for microorganism	Yes
microbio_resistotype	BLSE, MRSA, etc (comma-separated list)	No
microbio_pathogeny	Responsible for colonization or infection	No
microbio_comment	Free text	No
Host		
host_context	community; hospital/clinic; medico-social sector	No
host_travel	Recent trip abroad: yes or no	No
host_species	species of host	If sample_type == human or animal
host_zip	ZIP code of the host's home	
host_country	country of the host's home	

host_coordinate	latitude, longitude	No
host_age	age of the patient	Require ethical consent
host_sex	gender of the patient	
Host_clinic	Context clinic	Require ethical consent
study_ethical_consent	describes if patient signed a study ethical consent	No
Epidemiology		
grouped_cases	Linked to grouped cases: yes or no	No
institution_zip	ZIP code of hospital/clinic/medico social institution	No
Institution_country	country of hospital/clinic/medico social institution	No
Institution_context		
institution_name	name of hospital/clinic/medico social institution/farm where patient is treated	Require ethical consent
institution_ward	ward where patient is staying	
instution_room	room number where patient is staying	

- Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (AST) data

The system will support both qualitative and quantitative AST data such as those resulting from disk diffusion and broth dilution tests (MICs and/or SIR data as txt file). In order to represent AST data, we will define a data type designated “AST”. ASTs will be treated as data objects supporting data submission, access services and export to international databases.

We will aim with ASTs for a format that is flexible and complete. Any combination of bacterial species and antimicrobial will be supported as well as MIC and the classification using the RIS system (Table 2). all major testing platforms (Sensititre, MicroScan, VITEK and Phoenix) and standards (EUCAST, CLSI etc...) will be accepted. More uncommon methods will be added by using the free-text format of these sections.

Table 2: Metadata and data required for each combination of isolate/antibiotic provided

Required field	Description	Mandatory
sample_id	Sample ID	Yes
species	Microbial species	Yes
antibiotic_name	Antibiotic name from defined list	Yes
ast_standard	CLSI, CA-SFM, EUCAST, EUCAST-ECOFF, BSAC, DIN, SIR, WRG or	Yes
breakpoint_version	Version (e.i. 2015)	Yes
method	Broth dilution, Agar dilution, Agar diffusion or platform	Yes
platform	VITEK, Phoenix, MicroScan, Sensititre	No
measurement_sign	=, ≤ or ≥	Yes*
measurement	Fixed number	Yes*
measurement_units	µg/mL	Yes*
RIS_classification	intermediate, susceptible, resistant, non-susceptible, not defined	Yes*

* Will depend upon the technology used

- Sequencing file

The system will support paired-end and single-end short reads (formats fastq, fastq.gz and dsr), single-end long reads (formats fastq and fastq.gz), assembled data for complete genome sequences (formats fasta and gbk) and associated metadata (Table 3). In order to represent this omics data, we will define data types designated “reads” and “assembly”, which will be treated as data objects supporting data submission, access services and compatibility with external databases. Each reads and assembly objects will be linked to metadata and consequently to AST data if provided. The association will be asserted by linking the analysis object with the corresponding sample.

Table 3: Metadata required for sequencing and assembled data

Sequencing		Mandatory
DNA_extraction_kit	Kit used for DNA extraction	No
library_preparation_kit	Kit used for library preparation	No
sequencing_platform	Technology used for sequencing, e.g.,Illumina MiSeq,	Yes
Flow_cell_version	Version (Oxford Nanopore)	No
base_caller	Version (Oxford Nanopore)	No
Bioinformatics		Mandatory
quality_filtering_tool	Name (version) of the tool used for quality filtering reads	No
assembly_method	Mapping-based assembly; de-novo assembly	Yes
assembly_tool	Name (version) of the tool used for genome assembly	Yes
assembly_polishing	Name of the tools used for assembly polishing	No
reference_genome	Reference genome used for mapping (gbk and fasta formats)	No

- File resulting from data production

The system will store data resulting from analyses performed within the system. The system will trace the pipelines and the databases (version) used to produce the data, the user responsible for data production/modification and the date of last modification. In order to represent this data, we will define analysis types, which will be treated as data objects within the system (quality control, species identification/contamination, genes and SNP involved in resistance and virulence, resistotypes, pathovars, plasmidome, ST, phylogroup, serogroup, cgMLST, tree and/or SNP matrix and/or VCF file). They will support access services and will be linked to corresponding omics data (reads or/and assembly).

2. Data submission

To help data providers, a detailed protocol explaining the preparation of data and metadata form will be presented along with tools for batch creation from excel files. Building this support will require the development of tools for the validation and submission of incoming data and metadata. An interactive web page allowing manual creations will be developed for an easy alternative for data providers

registering a limited number of samples. This portal will also allow to update the metadata by batch and for a single sample.

3. Data production: bioinformatic functionalities

The data providers can perform analysis from omics data according to its own way and by using standardized and validated pipelines (Figure 1) allowing to extract key features of strains (e.g. quality control, species identification/contamination, genes and SNP involved in resistance and virulence, resistotypes, pathovars, plasmidome, mobilome, ST, phylogroup, serogroup, spa typing, cgMLST,), their clonality relatedness and if closely related isolates are already present in the system. The data produced will results from the analysis of a single sample (e.g. to determine the list of genes and SNPs involved in antibiotic resistance and virulence, the resistotypes, the pathovars, the sequence types, the phylogroups, the serogroups, and/or to produce annotated VCF file) and set of samples (e.g. to produce phylogenetic tree and SNP matrix). The data produced by own way processes will be stored at short term and data produced from the pipelines will be stored at long term.

Figure 1: data production from own-way processes and standardized pipelines

WGS data are *de novo* assembled and/or mapped against reference sequences, which is the basis for detecting genes and SNPs, and reconstructing a phylogeny. This process can be rather time-consuming and currently has a series of uncertainties, including differences between bioinformatics pipelines and pipeline specifications regarding quality controls, lack of epidemiological metadata, unavailability of non-outbreak-related isolates, etc... The quality controls and the standardisation of the analytical process will be a key element of our project. Because of uncertainties, we will initiated a quality assessment trial focusing on quality of the *de novo* assembly (contiguity metrics: cumulative contigs length, number of contigs, auN), bacterial phylogeny and resistance gene detection using published tools in order to assess matching with the meta-data and key aspects of sequencing, data analysis and clinical context. We expect

that the resulting data will allow us to establish standards (QC, tools and processing) improving the overall quality of sequencing and subsequent data analysis.

- **Own way processes (i.e., galaxy server)**

The system will provide suppliers with selected bioinformatics tools to process NGS data on their own way via a Galaxy server. The tools will cover the following fields of activity:

- Reads pre-processing (coverage estimation, low quality trimming, normalization)
- Kmer-based classification (taxonomic assignment, contamination checking)
- Quality control (QC for reads, assembly and SNP calling)
- *De novo* Assembler (short reads, long reads and hybrid)
- Automated annotation tools (prokka)
- *In silico* MLST, phylogrouping, serotyping, spa typing, LREfinder etc...
- Plasmid and mobilome analysis
- SNP caller and tree inference
- SNP caller and comparative genomics (SNP annotation)
- Pangenomic analysis

The resulting unstructured data will be only stored at short term (e.g. 6 months, to be defined).

- **Pipeline for standardized data and long-term storing**

The system will produce structured data for long term storing from one or several validated and standardized pipelines allowing to determine (Figure 2). The pipeline will be launched on data owner's initiative or will be triggered by public data release via an automated process. Genes and SNPs will be detected by one or several methods based on reads mapping and *de novo* reads assembling. The curation status of data will be set by an automated validation if the data and QCs are consistent. An alert will be notified to both the data owner and experts for manual curation if data are inconsistent (conflicting results and new variants) or did not reach QC thresholds (coverage and sequencing depth). New resistance mechanisms will be extracted and included in the database of the system after manually curation according to an updating procedure.

Figure 1: Pipeline producing standardized data for long-term storing

- **Development and advanced tools**

The system will include a development interface for beta testing tools and tools requiring controlled usages to maintain confidentiality, produce public health data or avoid server overload. They will be visible and accessible for the IT development team, could be shared with defined users or made public. This interface will manage for example:

- The setting for temporal and geographic real-time tracking of key bacterial lineages, resistotypes, plasmids and pathovars,
- Tools for discovery of new antibiotic resistance mechanisms (i.e. GWAS, PCM),
- Tools for phylogeny dating to identify the origin and the expansion of resistant clones,
- Tools epidemiological modelling for the inference of transmission chains, sources attribution and quantify their relative contribution in a “one health” perspective.

- **Databases required for jobs**

The database(s) for antibiotic resistance mechanisms will only include data known to induce a clinical impact on antimicrobial agent resistance. It will be maintained and curated by experts in the field (reference laboratories). The database will include protein variants, DNA data (e.g. promoters), SNPs and the associated reference sequences. Each resistance mechanism will be associated to the accession numbers in international databases, the antibiotic family targeted, the type of resistance mechanism (antibiotic modification, permeability alteration, efflux overexpression, antibiotic target modification, antibiotic target overproduction, antibiotic target protection, etc...) and hosting groups such as Gram-negative bacteria, Gram-positive bacteria, eubacteria, Mycobacteria, fungi or virus. The French reference

centre for antibiotic resistance has already developed such a database, from internal data and online international databases (NDARO, RESFINDER, CARD and BLDB).

The system will also include online databases for virulence genes (e.g. VFDB), kmer-based taxonomic classification (curated refseq database), MLST and cgMLST (e.g. pubMLST, BIGSdb-Pasteur, EnteroBase), and others databases such E. coli serotypes, E. coli phylogroup and replicons (CGE).

The databases will be updated according to a schedule and a validation procedure including a dataset testing.

B) File storage and management system for metagenomic data and metadata

1. Data types (formats, size)

Various types of related metagenomics data will be imported, transformed and organized in the ABRomics system:

- Metagenomic sample data with fastq files (paired-end and single-end reads) produced by different technologies (Illumina, ThermoFisher, DNBSeg, Pacific Bio., Oxford Nanopore...) accompanied with a set of metadata including sample description, sequencing protocols, host features, epidemiologic data. Collected metadata will follow requirements described in table 1 (section genomics). When available and under data regulation considerations, additional metadata could be collected and organized in the ABRomics system, in particular with more informative phenotypic information concerning the host including its antibiotic intake habits and associated clinical aspects. Moreover, complementary standardized metadata could be collected (for example, Human metagenomic samples could be described with IHMS metadata requirements).
- Metagenomic assembly data (contigs, genes and MAGs) will be produced in fasta format and will be accompanied with the same kind of required metadata in table 3 of section 'genomics'. The ABRomics platform will make available gene, contig and MAG host-specific catalogs (redundant or not) for downstream analysis.
- Structural and functional annotations (OG, KO, ARG, BGC (biosynthetic gene cluster)) of each assembly data (genes, contigs, MAGs). Associated metadata will precise the annotation protocols (pipeline, software, database version, parameters...).
- Taxonomic affiliations (marker gene-based, genome-based) of each assembly data (genes, contigs, MAGs). Associated metadata will precise the annotation protocols (pipeline, software, database version, parameters...).

2. Data storage & management

According to the different data regulation considerations, three data storage ways will be available including importation, curation and processing for:

- **The public metagenomic samples with scientific and medical interest for antimicrobial resistance research:** these metagenomic datasets and related processed datasets will be available for the end-users of the ABRomics platform.
- **The internal metagenomic data produced by the different partners in the context of ABRomics project:** these metagenomic datasets and related processed datasets will be available only for the members of the ABRomics project but could be made available for all the scientific community when published.
- **The private metagenomic data of the end-users of the ABRomics platform:** these metagenomic datasets and related processed datasets will be available only by the owners of the data. Submission of private data will be authorized after endorsement by the ABRomics platform. A requested project form will describe the global aims for using the platform and how the datasets will be relevant with the antimicrobial resistance research. ABRomics platform will provide recommendations and obligations before submitting data, in particular in terms of mandatory and/or optional metadata and data privacy respect (in regards of GDPR, health data regulation and patient consents for examples). For the latter, the ABRomics platform will be required to submit anonymised or pseudonymised data.

Raw metagenomic sequencing data will be a pre-requirement for the downstream processing and analysis. As these sequencing data are very huge and can be stored on external repositories (public repositories or attached to the sequencing producer facilities) but also in regards to the data regulation, the ABRomics platform will not undertake to systematically keep the sequencing data. However, directly after submission, the raw metagenomic sequencing data will be filtered for the quality and for the host-related reads (to ensure data privacy).

For storing the metagenomic data (sequencing and derived data), we will rely on the data model proposed for the genomics data and on the IFB computing facilities deployed in the context of the MUDIS4LS project. These facilities will provide large data space and HPC resources compliant for the metagenomic data processing and several recommendations and guidelines for managing critical health data and for making datasets interoperable.

3. Data production: bioinformatic functionalities

A classical primary pipeline could be :

- 1- submission of metagenomic sample
- 2- pre-processing of the sample (QC, host removing)
- 3- querying the arg databases (blast...) : by reads, by genes (need assembly)
- 4- displaying the results to the user

Metagenomics Workflows :

- Data submission and pre-processing :
 - Submission of metagenomic data will be accompanied by guidelines including a mandatory metadata list. We will rely on actual initiative on data brokering in order to standardize the metagenomic data submission on ABRomics platform

- Quality control pre-processing with commonly used dedicated tools (fastp...) and host related reads removal. For this latter task, we will rely on the effort initiated in EU IHMCSA project and MMHP project..
- This workflow is mandatory because we have to consider that end-users of the platform will be not experts with metagenomic bioinformatic tools.
- This workflow should address the various sequencing technologies (Illumina, Proton, MGISEQ, Oxford Nanopore, Pacific Bioscience...)
- Taxonomic profiling :
 - Different well-recognized tools and databases will be embedded in the workflow, like mOTU2, metaphlan, MGS/MSP, Kraken...
 - This workflow will permit to quickly scan crucial species in terms of public health which are expected to harbour antibiotic resistance genes and/or virulence genes (see for example WHO priority pathogens : <https://www.who.int/news/item/27-02-2017-who-publishes-list-of-bacteria-for-which-new-antibiotics-are-urgently-needed>)
- Special gene abundance profiling :
 - Based on read mapping, this workflow will permit to scan presence/absence of genes in metagenomic samples and to compute their abundance.
- Assembly
 - According to the representativity of reference databases used to scan metagenomes, this workflow will permit to assemble metagenomic reads in order to enlarge reference databases with new genes and new genomes.
- Binning
 - By adding new metagenomic samples into the platform, binning workflow will be implemented in order to reconstruct new bins or enlarge existing bins with new genes never assembled.
- MAG and genome collection
 - This workflow will permit reconstructing MAGs from the different uploaded metagenomic samples.
 - Additionally, it could be interesting to connect genome collections managed in the genomic section of the ABRomics-DB, in order to increase the possibility of annotation and querying.
- Gene annotations
 - In particular, genes reconstructed from metagenomic samples will be annotated for ARG (or virulence) using dedicated tools and databases. IN this context, workflow described in the “genomics” section will be used.
- Genome annotations
 - In addition to taxonomic and functional annotations, contextualization of the genomes (in terms of potential pathogenicity and/or ARG content and/or gene dissemination potential...) will be an added value for the platform.

4. Required microbiological databases

- ARG databases (with various layers according to the user/purpose: for clinicians, for ecologists, for public health specialists, etc) : federated database in order to facilitate access to the data. Of notice, ARGs databases need to be continuously updated and open to ecosystems other than the gut (e.g. the respiratory one for which targeted-antibiotics exist - ie inhaled ones-).
- Connection with phenotype (in relation to the NRCs), taxonomic origin if known : regularly scan of external ARG databases for new genes and submission to NCR for expert curation/annotation (phenotype, origin...).
- Connection with ARG source ecosystem (metagenome sample, gene catalog, host...) : allow users to quickly query the presence of an ARG in a particular ecosystem, or group of patients, etc.
- Connection with virulence databases (VFDB, PATRIC_VF...) : co-presence of ARG and VF
- Connection with MGE (Mobile Genetic Elements) databases : addressing the question of transmissibility

New Appendix: Production of -omics data by the partners of the ABRomics-PF

ABRomics – Omics data production by ABRomics-PF partners

Team name	Contact person	Affiliation	Production of -omics data:
DSP	Jean-Yves Madec	Anses	genomics
Département Médicament et Technologies pour la santé	Jean Armengaud	CEA	metagenomics
CNR des Campylobacters et des Hélicobacters	Philippe Lehours	INSERM	proteomics
CNR des Campylobacters et des Hélicobacters	Quentin Jehanne	INSERM	genomics
CNR des Staphylocoques	Francois Vandenesch	Hospices Civils de Lyon / Université Lyon 1	genomics
CNR résistance aux antibiotiques	Vincent Cottier	CHU de Rennes	genomics
CNR de la résistance aux antibiotiques	Patrick Plesiat	CHU de Besançon	transcriptomics
CNR résistance aux antibiotiques	Richard Bonnet	CHU de Clermont-Ferrand	genomics
CNR résistance aux antibiotiques	Thierry Naas	CHU Paris Saclay	genomics
Dendritic cells and immunoregulation in transplantation and immunopathology	Jeremie Poschmann	INSERM	transcriptomics
Host Pathogen Interactions, Inflammation and Mucosal Immunity	Antoine Roquilly	Université de Nantes	epigenomics
Dynamique des génomes et adaptation microbienne	Nathalie Leblond	Université de Lorraine- INRAE	transcriptomics
InfoBioStat	Nicolas Pons	INRAE	metabolomics
Plasticité Génomique Biodiversité Antibiorésistance	Benoit Doublet	INRAE	genomics
Anti-infectieux : supports moléculaires des résistances et innovations thérapeutiques	Olivier Barraud	Université Limoges, Inserm, CHU Limoges	metagenomics
IAME Infection, Antimicrobiens, Modélisation, Evolution	Etienne Ruppé	INSERM	genomics
PHYSE	Patricia Liznar-Fajardo	Université de Montpellier	metagenomics
Micro-organismes et interactions avec les	Jean-Christophe Auguet	CNRS	metagenomics
CRBIP (Biological Resources Center of the Institut Pasteur)	Sylvain Brisse	CRBIP	genomics
Ecology and Evolution of Antibiotic Resistance	Philippe Glaser	Institut Pasteur	metagenomics
Plateforme BioPark d'Archamps	Philippe Bulet	CRUGA, IAB, Inserm U1209, CNRSUMR5309, site distant	genomics
Analyse de biomolécules par spectrométrie de masse	Jérôme Lemoine	Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1	proteomics

Use case descriptions

Use Case 1: Detection and investigation of outbreak involving multidrug resistant bacteria

Coordinator

P. Plésiat, NRC Antibiotic Resistance (Besançon), Bacteriology

Team members

A. Birer, NRC Antibiotic Resistance (Clermont-Ferrand), Bioinformatic

R. Bonnet, NRC Antibiotic Resistance (Clermont-Ferrand), Bacteriology

R. Beyrouthy, NRC Antibiotic Resistance (Clermont-Ferrand), Bacteriology

P. Lehours, NRC for Campylobacters and Helicobacters (Bordeaux), Bacteriology

Q. Jehanne, NRC for Campylobacters and Helicobacters (Bordeaux), Bioinformatic

Objective

The goal of this use case is to demonstrate the contribution of the ABRomics platform in the investigation of hospital or veterinary clinic outbreaks involving multidrug resistant (mdr) Gram-negative pathogens.

Outline

Some mdr strains are able to actively diffuse within human populations, within animal populations, or both. Some can also persist in environmental reservoirs, from which patients or animals can be contaminated. Because of this complex landscape, identification of the transmission pathways that eventually lead to small or large infection outbreaks may be challenging, especially when involving clones able to survive or thrive in multiple ecosystems. Spatio-temporal analysis of the diffusion of such clones is therefore essential to implement appropriate control measures. Given that antibiotic resistance can be transmitted among bacteria through horizontal gene transfers, mobile genetic elements such as plasmids and ICEs (Integrative Conjugative Elements) must also be included in epidemiological surveys.

1 Transmissible clones of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as well as *Campylobacters* and *Helicobacter pylori* are prone to accumulate resistance mechanisms up to becoming refractory to most antibiotic treatments. These so-called “high-risk” clones need to be detected and their diffusion carefully surveyed at the local (healthcare facilities), regional, national and international levels. Through cgMLST, and SNP analyses, the ABRomics platform will efficiently compare and dissect the genome sequences of clinical and environmental strains isolated during presumed hospital or veterinary clinic outbreaks, or exhibiting particular resistance traits (e.g., carbapenem or colistin resistance). The platform will be open to single users (e.g., medical biologists, researchers) or institutions (e.g., NRCs) with access to metagenomic data depending upon the authorization level. Based on these inputs, an interactive map of emergent or known “high-risk” clones will be drawn in real-time, and a warning made for confirmed cases of outbreak.

2. Self-transmissible and mobilizable plasmids carrying relevant ARGs (e.g., encoding carbapenemase, ESBL or colistin resistance) need to be traced in order to document their prevalence and diffusion across bacterial strains or species. The plasmid content of mdr strains of *E. coli*, *K. pneumoniae*, *E. cloacae*, *A. baumannii*, *P. aeruginosa* and *Campylobacters* will thus be systematically characterized (e.g., plasmid size, genes, incompatibility group, predicted transmissibility) from the genomic data submitted to the ABRomics platform. A comprehensive plasmid database

will next be constructed in order to improve our knowledge of resistance replicons diffusing in different reservoirs and different geographic areas. Presence of specific virulence genes on plasmids will be screened and reported to the platform's users.

Scientific issues

- *Preliminary issue: Confirmation of species identification*
- *Issue 1: Identification of bacterial clones involved in outbreaks*
- *Issue 2: Identification of resistance and virulence determinants*
- *Issue 3: Spatio-temporal analysis of resistance spread*

Tasks for UC1 supported by WP1, WP2 and WP6

1. Submission of the dataset: paired-end short reads, metadata and AST data
2. Quality of reads: trimming and assessment of the quality of reads
3. Taxonomic classification: classification of reads among taxon using a taxonomic database, and detection of bacterial contaminants
4. Assembly of whole genome sequences and assessment of the quality of the assemblies by standard indexes (N50, Depth, etc...)
5. Clonal relationships among bacterial isolates: computing of sequence types (MLST) and core genome alleles (cgMLST), and update of corresponding databases if needed; construction of dendrograms and associated distance matrix from cgMLST data, and identification of closely related strains using thresholds
6. Detection of genes or SNPs associated with resistance and virulence; characterization of plasmids; assessment of quality detection (depth, coverage, identity and allele fraction); update ABR and virulence databases if required
7. Spatio-temporal analysis: generate spatio-temporal views (i.e., nextstrain) of data selected by the user among sequence types, core genome clusters, resistance mechanisms, virulence genes, AST data and metadata
8. Submission of annotated genomes to ENA/GenBank

Deliverables for UC1

1. Quality controls about the sequences, the assemblies and the detections
2. Clonality relationships of MDR strains
3. Resistome and virulome of MDR strains
4. Spatio-temporal distribution of resistotypes, pathotypes and associated metadata
5. Benchmarking about strain molecular typing and ABR gene detections

Perspectives

1. Plasmid reconstruction, structural evolution and spread analysis
2. Reconstruction of transmission chains
3. Modelling resistance spread and outbreaks

Use Case diagram

Detection and investigation of outbreaks involving multidrug resistant bacteria

Workflow for sequencing data analysis in UC1 using tools and knowledge databases provided by WP2

Use Case 2: One Health approach to the emergence, transition and dissemination of antimicrobial resistance in *Acinetobacter baumannii*

Coordinator

X. Charpentier, Inserm U1111/CIRI (Lyon), Bacteriology, Project leader (Ab-One PPR project)

Team members

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Objective

This use case aims to demonstrate the contribution of the ABRomics platform in the analysis of antimicrobial resistance in a One Health framework. Specifically, the project will require to store a large set of *Acinetobacter baumannii* (Ab) genomes sampled from different environments, along with their metadata and to perform a joint statistical and ecological analysis of these samples.

Outline

Ab is a bacterium responsible for a wide range of severe hospital-acquired infections with a steadily increasing prevalence of multi-drug resistant strains throughout the world. The WHO has declared it as a priority pathogen for antimicrobial research efforts, a status reinforced by the recent discovery of hypervirulent strains. The identification in human and animal infections of strains from the same clonal group or carrying the same resistance genes, as well as recent discoveries of Ab from environmental sources (animal and terrestrial), call for an integrated "One Health" approach for this pathogen. Ab-one will develop 5 research axes to capture Ab populations (diversity/pangenome/resistome) on a global scale, to analyze their structure and eco-evolutionary dynamics, to identify AMR genes, to assess their intra- and inter-genomic movements, their association with virulence traits and finally, to develop mathematical models of the emergence, transmission and dissemination of AMR in Ab.

The One Health approach developed by this use case, based on a large data collection and analysis using extremely diverse and complementary expertise, could serve as a model for other emerging pathogens.

Scientific issues

The project will address the dynamics of AMR emergence, transmission and dissemination in *Ab* from (and to) the natural, animal environments and clinical environments.

Issues

1. Establishing the first global One Health network to capture the dynamics of Ab populations (diversity/pangenome/resistome) evolving in contrasting ecological conditions (from pristine to highly anthropized ecosystems, on a global scale (Europe, Caribbean Islands, Indian Ocean)).
2. Characterize the environmental microbial communities in which Ab evolves and identify associated selective pressures.
3. Characterize the population structure of Ab (strain diversity within populations, variability between populations, between environments -natural environments, animals, humans)

4. Identification of the AMR genes, their associations with mobile genetic elements and dynamics, horizontal gene transfer events
5. Phenotypic characterization of the One Health collection of Ab isolates (antibiotic resistance levels, ability to acquire AMR genes)
6. Exploit genomic and phenotypic data with association studies to explore the genetic basis of AMR.
7. Assess the relative importance of horizontal gene transfers (HGTs) and mobile genetic elements (MGEs) on the population dynamics of Ab and the emergence, transmission and dissemination of AMR.

Tasks for UC2 supported by WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP6

1. Submission of metabarcoding sequencing data of longitudinal sampling of environmental microbial communities in which Ab resides, along with physico-chemical metadata of the environments. Support: WP1 (T.1.4, T.1.6), WP6 (T.6.1)
2. Processing of metabarcoding data to reveal the dynamics of the environmental microbial communities in which Ab evolves. Support: WP2 (T.2.4, T.2.5)
3. Submission of large datasets of metadata and genome sequencing data (illumina and nanopore) of Ab isolates from 5 geographical areas (n=~3000). Support: WP1 (T.1.4, T.1.6), WP6 (T.6.1)
4. Assembly and uniform annotation of the Ab genomes. Detect AMR genes, MGEs and recombination events. Analysis of gene flow in the species and closely related ones. Support: WP2 (T.2.4, T.2.5), WP3 (T.3.3.1, T.3.3.3)
5. Experimental determination of MIC levels to current and next generations of antibiotics (~25 antibiotics). Quantify the ability of the isolate to undergo HGT (2 distinct assays) and interact with the host (8 distinct assays)
6. Conduct of gene-level and nucleotide-level genome-wide association studies to link AMR and virulence phenotypes to genotypes. Support: WP2 (T.2.4, T.2.5)
7. Development of ecosystem models that encompass relevant phenomena from the molecular to the ecosystem scale. Support: WP3 (T.3.3.4, T.3.3.5)

Deliverables for UC2

1. First One Health sample collection campaign.
2. Longitudinal biotic and abiotic characteristics of the natural environments of Ab.
3. Genome sequence and MIC profiles of ~3000 diverse isolates.
4. Annotation of the genomes, construction of pan and core genomes.
5. Population structure of the species and related bacteria.
6. Analysis of the flux of genes within and between compartments.
7. Identification of the putative genetic basis of antibiotic resistance and environmental association.
8. Natural transformation and conjugation rates, barriers to HGT.
9. Identification of MDR Ab strains with the potential to cause outbreaks.
10. New hypotheses regarding genotype-phenotype links.
11. Construction of an integrated, multi-scale, modeling framework.
12. Modeling of the MGE-community and resistome dynamics.

Perspectives :

1. Establishing a One Health, global study on a WHO priority. A template for other antibiotic-resistant emerging pathogens.
2. Resolving the key parameters of emergence to be monitored, and providing new operational perspectives as a function of therapeutic practices in the clinical and veterinary settings to preserve our current and future therapeutic arsenal.

Use case diagram

Use Case 3: Application of Meta-PanGenomic concept for tracking antibioresistance in metagenomic samples

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Objective

This use case aims to demonstrate the potential application of Meta-PanGenomic concept for tracking at the species and strain levels associations between antimicrobial resistance and pathogenicity in the context of human microbiota.

Outlines

Reconstruction of metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs) has recently become a common task for microbiome studies in particular to compare genetic content of species across metagenomic samples. However, it has been shown that the gene content captured in a MAG can highly differ from the one obtained by the genome sequencing of the corresponding isolate (Meziti, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.02593-20>; Maguire, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1099/mgen.0.000436>). Missing genes in MAGs are commonly harbored by genomic regions with atypical tetranucleotide frequency that make difficult the application of assembly and binning tools to reconstruct them. These atypical genomic regions correspond frequently to mobile genetic elements that may contain virulence factors and antimicrobial resistance genes (ARG) (Oliveira, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-00808-w>). Long read technologies (like Oxford Nanopore or Pacific Bioscience) could be a game-changer in the next few years and will be useful in particular for discovery purposes rather than quantitative estimation of known variations.

Therefore, in order to better characterize and quantify the dissemination of antimicrobial resistance and its association with potential pathogenicity, we propose for this application an innovative approach combining the use of metagenomic data and pangenome graph structure (Gautreau, 2020, <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007732>). For a given microbial species, a pangenome graph combines the genomic content of all the microbial strains (optionally enriched with high-quality MAGs and metagenomic long read assemblies) where nodes represent the gene families and edges their genomic neighborhood. As said, antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes are associated with specific genetic contexts including pathogenicity islands and/or mobile genetic elements. Therefore, the gene families of the pangenome graph are partitioned in core and accessory elements in order to identify, in association with their functional annotation, specific regions of interest which are variable in the pangenome. In the context of the identification of a pathogenic bacterial strain from an environmental or clinical sample, a direct mapping of metagenomics reads on the nodes of the species pangenome graph will highlight relevant regions containing ARG and/or virulence factors. In the case of complex samples with several strains of the same species, the distribution of the mapping abundances along the pangenome graph can be analyzed with adapted signal deconvolution methods to unravel strain composition in a sample with their relative abundances and specific variable genomic regions. To summarize, the described approach could be named Meta-PanGenomic as it uses a pangenome database queried by the metagenomic reads to deeply characterize and quantify antimicrobial-resistant strains.

The development of the Meta-PanGenomic graph method will be conducted in strong interaction with WP3 of ABROmics, particularly in Task 3.3.1. The strategies already developed by the LABGeM partner using PPanGGOLiN software (Gautreau, 2020, <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007732>) will be a starting point. Aims of the use-case will be to iterate specific methodological needs with WP3 and to develop, benchmark and validate the approach. Interactions with WP2 will be required in order to address metagenomic data processing with standardized pipelines of ABROmics and pangenome annotation for antimicrobial resistance genes, virulence factors and mobile genetic elements.

This use-case will be applied on well-chosen metagenomic datasets in order to demonstrate the technical feasibility and the scientific interest in the context of antibioresistance.

Dataset 1. Demonstrate and benchmark the use of the Meta-PanGenomic graph concept to characterize diversity and dissemination of ARGs in complex microbial ecosystems. To address this issue, we propose to use the recent EcoZUR cohort (Peña-Gonzalez, 2019, <http://doi.org/10.1128/AEM.01820-19>) focused on the role of *E. coli* on diarrhea in children. This study makes available metagenomic samples of children with or without diarrhea. Causal agents (*E. coli*) have been isolated and sequenced from each sample of diarrheic children. Here, known causal agents will be tracked by mapping metagenomic samples on a specific pangenome graph aggregating reference genomes of *E. coli* isolates including those sequenced in the EcoZUR study. This dataset will permit to benchmark and validate the development of the Meta-PanGenomic approach. In particular, we will explore the impact of adding variable-quality MAGs to pangenome graphs for the detection of variable regions. To note that this dataset could be completed by the German outbreak study (Loman, 2013, <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.3231>).

Dataset 2. Explore the gut microbiota evolution after antibiotic exposure. We propose to address a potential application of pangenomic graph analysis in clinical metagenomic by using a published study related to the effect of antibiotics intake on the gut microbiota stability (Palleja, 2018, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-018-0257-9>). This study provides metagenomic samples of gut microbiota of 12 healthy men over a 6-month period following a 4-day intervention with a cocktail of 3 last-resort antibiotics (meropenem, gentamicin and vancomycin). Pangenome graphs will be analysed for gut species enriched quickly after antibiotics intake in order to detect resistant bacterial strains and potentially associated with microbiota virulence enrichment. Using longitudinal metagenomic samples, we will also explore the long-term impact of antibiotics intake on the microbiota changes and potential antimicrobial resistance gene acquisitions and emergence of pathogen resistant bacterial strains.

Dataset 3. Characterize the resistome of large populations. The French Gut Project and Million Microbiomes of Human Project (MMHP) (in which MetaGenoPolis partner is coordinator and member, respectively) will characterize the microbiota diversity across large populations. These initiatives will make open access every year the metagenomic data accompanied with an anonymized minimal set of metadata describing each volunteer. For ABROmics consortium, access to such large cohorts will permit to explore the resistome diversity and its evolution according to age, geography, or certain clinical status. We propose to investigate these datasets using the pangenomic graph concept in order to map the 'world-wide' antimicrobial resistance diversity of *E. coli* and the other 'most wanted bacteria' of the WHO.

Scientific issues

Using Meta-PanGenome graph methods together with ABROmics platform services, the use-case will address scientific issues related to antibioresistance in link with the human microbiome:

1. Characterization of human gut microbiota enrichment for antimicrobial resistant strains and associated virulence factors after antibiotics intake.
2. Characterization of long-term impact of antibiotics intake on microbiota changes and antimicrobial resistance gene acquisition.

- Correlation between human gut resistome of large population and host features.

Tasks for UC3 supported by WP2, WP3 and WP6

- Submission of metagenomic datasets to the ABROmics platform;** Support: WP2, WP6.
- Development, benchmark and validation of Meta-PanGenome graph method** including graph construction, read mapping, deconvolution method and visualization; Support WP3, WP6.
- Functional annotation of pangenome for specialized genes** including ARG, virulence factors and mobile genetic elements; Support WP2.
- Development of a pangenome database of bacterial species with medical interest;** Support WP2, WP3.

Deliverables

- A Meta-PanGenome software to estimate strain abundance and their variable genomic regions from metagenomic samples.
- An up-to-date comprehensive pangenome resource of the most relevant species to study ABR in microbiota including functional annotations
- Web interface for the visualization of the ARG location on the pangenome graph.
- Integration of the Meta-PanGenomic approach in the ABROmics-PF as a ready-to-use tool for investigating antimicrobial resistance dissemination in complex microbial ecosystems particularly in other use-cases of ABROmics project.
- Guidelines and reproducible workflows for applying Meta-PanGenomic approach in ABROmics-PF.

Use-case diagram

Meta-Pangenomic use-case diagram describing roles and interactions with WP in the development and integration of the Meta-PanGenomic concept in the ABRomics-PF and its application in ARG tracking in human microbiome.

Use Case 4: Pulmonary infections

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Objective

This use case aims to demonstrate the contribution of the ABRomics platform in the analysis of antimicrobial resistance in the context of pulmonary infections.

Outline

The use case is presented using the example of 2 types of lung infection corresponding to 2 different clinical and ecological contexts:

1° Chronic lung infections that require repeated and **long-lasting antibiotic courses**. The use of the ABRomics platform will be illustrated through the BEACH study (funding: PHRC-I API18/B/072 + Vaincre la Mucoviscidose), a prospective multicentre (n=11 centres in France) study (P.I. G. Héry-Arnaud) which aims to characterise the pulmonary and intestinal microbiome of newborns with cystic fibrosis (CF). The longitudinal metagenomic data generated by this program will enable the deciphering of the evolution of the bronchopulmonary **community-acquired resistome** during the first antibiotic cures (**oral and inhaled** routes) received by CF **children** in the first 2 years of life.

2° Acute lung infections, which are infections with a vital prognosis in the short term and which require rapidly effective antibiotic cures (**short-lasting antibiotic courses**, mostly **intravenously**). The use of the [name] platform will be illustrated through the HAP² study (funding: H2020 #847782), a prospective international study on hospital-acquired pneumonia led by an international consortium (P.I. A. Roquilly), and the COVARDS study (funding ANR Flash-COVID), a French cohort of patients with severe COVID-19 pneumonia. Samples and raw data from these studies are already available. Multi-omic approach that integrates host-microbiota interactions generated by this program will enable the characterisation of the pulmonary ARGs distribution of hospital-acquired pneumonia (HAP) in intubated **adult** patients in a **nosocomial** context (HAP²) and in **community**-acquired pneumonia (COVARDS).

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is one of the most frequent and threatening bacteria linked with these both clinical entities, and belongs to the WHO global priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacterial species. Multidrug-resistant *P. aeruginosa* (**MDR-PA**) is an important and growing issue in the care of patients with CF. In VAPs, a high attributable mortality is observed despite adequate antimicrobial treatment that is increased in the presence of MDR-PA strains. The *Pseudomonas* NRC (headed by P. Plésiat) is currently developing a program to establish ARGs from clinical strains of different sources (including VAP and CF) and with well-defined antibiotypes. These WGS-derived data will enable PA-specific ARGs to be identified in the metagenomic data generated by the BEACH and HAP² studies.

Scientific issues

The three projects (BEACH, HAP2, COVARDS) will address specific lung AMR issues that will be resolved by the ABRomics PF.

1. Preliminary issue: *How naïve (in regards with AMR) is the lung ecosystem of a CF newborn/patient at the admission in an ICU?*
2. Issue 1: *What are the differences between several classes of pulmonary antibiotics in terms of selection pressure in the lungs?*
3. Issue 2: *How does the commensal microbiome act on pathogens-related ARGs?*
4. Issue 3: *How does the host act on ARGs development in the lung?*

Tasks for UC4 supported by WP2, WP3 and WP6

1. **Submission of the datasets** (metagenomics, transcriptomics, metabolomics, patients metadata, Pseudomonas NRC data) to the AbROmics platform; Support: WP1 and WP6
2. **Characterization of the lung microbiome**; Support: WP2
3. **Integration of the host transcriptome and metabolome matrix data**; Support: WP3
4. **Characterization of the ARGs spectrum of lung samples** in (i) Antibiotics-naïve CF children and 2 years-old CF children, (ii) Adult patients hospitalized in ICU before/after initiation of the antimicrobial treatment. This includes existing ARGs: NRC sources (based on WGS from bacterial strains collection from different reservoirs or type of infection) and calculating ARGs: Mustard sources (ARGs prediction based on protein homology modelling) - Support: WP2
5. **Characterization of the ARGs expansion within the lung ecosystem**: development of applications to integrate both WGS and metagenomics data collected at different time-points and under different antimicrobial treatment courses - Support: WP3
6. **Characterization of the ARGs of the lung commensals and pathogen *P. aeruginosa*** using developments of meta-PanGenomics - Support: WP3
7. **Correlation between commensal microbiome and ARGs expansion** using developments of meta-PanGenomics - Support: WP3
8. **Correlation between host features and ARGs expansion** : ARGs multi-omics integration - Support: WP3

Deliverables for UC4

1. Lung microbiome characterization
2. Lung host transcriptome and metabolome characterization
3. ARGs characterization of antimicrobial-naïve lungs in children and adult patients
4. ARGs characterization after lung antimicrobial courses
5. ARGs expansion in the lung under antimicrobial selection pressure
6. Benchmarking of MustARD database and PCM workflow in the lung ecosystem
7. *P. aeruginosa* ARGs characterization from lung clinical strains isolated in different epidemiological contexts (community- or hospital-acquired infections)

8. Lung commensals ARGs characterization
9. Benchmarking of Meta-PanGenomics Graph application in the lung ecosystem
10. Development of an ARGs database and workflows specific to the lung ecosystem taking into account the temporal and multi-omics scales

Perspectives

1. Identification of predictive biomarkers of ARGs selection
2. Selection of antimicrobials with the lowest selection pressure in the lungs

Use case diagram

Lung infection use case diagram describing how physicians, microbiologists and National Reference Centres (NRC) will find the support of the AbROmics-PF to integrate their data and answer the 3 essential questions (circled in black) brought by the BEACH, COVARDS and HAP2 studies on the issue of antimicrobial resistance specific to the pulmonary ecosystem

Use Case 5: One Health dissemination of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) through aquatic environments (continental, oceanic and waste water)

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Objective

This use case aims to explore the role of different aquatic environments (waste water, continental and oceanic) in the dissemination of the antimicrobial resistance (AMR) thanks to the contribution of the ABRomics platform

Outline

The use case is presented using the AMR data obtained from oceanic (MARBEC-IRD team), continental (irrigation scheme, underground water and rivers, freshwater aquaculture) (MIVEGEC, HSM, ISEM-IRD team; RESINFIT-INSERM team; PGBA-INRAE team) and wastewater (MIVEGEC, TransVIHMI-IRD team; RESINFIT-INSERM team; PGBA-INRAE team). Other public data sources may be used if relevant.

1° Oceanic waters

In the context of several projects (such as EXPLOI, PLASTIPATH and NYMPHE), samples were collected from various sources (water, sediments, fishes and plastics) to determine the circulation of AMR in oceanic environments. Plastics are included as they harbour pathogens known to be involved in animal and human epidemics. Thus, plastics and

their associated antibiotic resistant pathogens in oceanic ecosystems can be transferred to marine animals ingesting plastics, and from them ultimately to humans who consume them.

Using the ABRomics platform, metagenomics and genomics data obtained from these samples will be confronted with various parameters (e.g. nutrient concentrations, temperature, salinity, antibiotic concentrations, precipitations), spatial (distance to the coast) and sociologic parameters (density of population, density of aquaculture exploitations) including local, regional and global human and animal AMR data to evaluate the determinants and risks of transmission in these environments.

2° Continental waters

The goal here is to investigate the contribution of continental waters to the transmission and dissemination of AMR and its impact on human, animal and environmental health (ZAARHYPOTTER project). In addition, we aim to understand the selection factors and spread of AMR in irrigation, drainage systems and aquaculture farms that can carry various kinds of pollutants (Antibiotic Resistance Genes - ARGs, antibiotic resistant bacteria - ARB, antibiotic residues and metals (MIVEGEC project, Bac Hung Gai project, TRANS-One Health project, WarmAqua). The sampling will be multiple: water, sediments, biofilms and sea fauna (fishes, shrimps, etc.). In these projects, we have collected microbiological data, metagenomics (bacterial diversity and resistome) and genomics (resistant bacterial genomes associated with resistance mechanisms) data as well as various parameters such as physical, geographical, climatic and chemical (natural and pollutant chemical composition) factors. The analysis of data according to the various parameters and the confrontation with local, regional and global AMR data using the ABRomics platform will help determine the risk factors for the detection and dissemination of AMR in these environments.

3° Waste waters

In the context of multicentre projects (CIRCUS, AMR Sud AVIESAN project (in review); ARCAHE, FSPI project, PRE-EMPT, TRANS-One Health project), we are – and will be - collecting wastewater samples together with human, animal and environmental (upstream/downstream rivers, soils) samplings. The overall objective is to characterize the circulation of AMR between human, animal and environmental compartments within the same living space, using a “One health” approach. The specific objectives are : (i) to characterize the resistance profiles of Enterobacteriaceae in these different compartments using culturomics, metagenomics and genomics; (ii) to determine and compare the proportion of multiresistant Enterobacteriaceae (MRE) in humans, animals and in waste waters; (iii) to characterize and compare the genome of MRE isolated in each compartment in order to identify the likely pathways of AMR circulation and identify the role of waste water in this transmission; and (iv) to describe the bacterial diversity and resistome through metagenomics. These data will be analysed together with data collected in humans and animals, and confronted to local, regional and global data available on AMR.

Scientific issues

The project will address the role and contribution of water environments to the AMR, particularly in the dissemination of ARGs and ARB that will be available through the ABRomics PF.

1. characterization of bacterial population diversity, resistome and bacterial genomes including resistance mechanisms in the various aquatic environments;
2. determination of specificities and/or similarities in terms of bacterial diversity, ARGs and ARB in the different water samplings (water fauna, plastics, sediments, continental and oceanic water, waste water) environments;
3. determination of ARGs and ARB distribution according to the water characteristics (chemical (metal, antibiotic residues), geographical or climatic data);
4. Comparison of aquatic AMR data (ARGs and ARB) obtained with global human, animal and environmental AMR data;
5. Modelisation and evaluation of transmission risk.

Tasks for UC5 supported by WP2 and WP3

1. Submission of the datasets (metagenomics, WGS, metadata, microbiological data, water characteristics) to the ABRomics platform; Support WP2;
2. Characterization of the bacterial diversity and of the resistome in the various water environments;
3. Characterization of enterobacterial strains and resistance mechanisms in the various environments
4. Characterization of enterobacterial population and resistance mechanisms in the different types of samples (water fauna, sediments, oceanic, continental and waste waters); Support: WP3 3.1.4, 3.3.4, 3.3.5;
5. Characterization of the ARGs expansion within water ecosystems; Support: WP3 (development of applications to integrate both WGS and metagenomics data collected at different settings and under different water environments) Tasks 3.1.4, 3.3.4, 3.3.5;
6. Evaluation of risk by comparison with global human and animal AMR data; Support: WP3 3.1.3, 3.1.4, 3.2.2, 3.3.5;

Deliverables for UC5

1. Water bacterial population characterization in the different water samples (water fauna, sediments, water, plastics) and ecosystems (oceanic, continental and waste waters);
2. Water bacterial resistome characterization in the different water samples (water fauna, sediments, water, plastics) and ecosystems (oceanic, continental and waste waters);
3. Bacterial genome and resistance mechanisms characterization
4. ARGs and enterobacterial genomes distribution according to the different water samples (water fauna, sediments, water, plastics) and ecosystems (oceanic, continental and waste waters);
5. Potential role of water in the dissemination of AMR by comparison with global AMR data;
6. Development of an ARGs and MRE database and workflows specific to the water ecosystems considering the spatial scales and water characteristics.

Perspectives

1. Identification of predictive AMR (ARGs and ARBs) dissemination factors
2. Evaluation of respective degrees of involvement of the different water ecosystems and water fauna in the dissemination of AMR.

Use case diagram

General diagram of bioproject data processing on the ABRomics-PF for several research studies related to AMR dissemination in aquatic environments. Data types, interactions with the ABRomics-PF components and scientific objectives to be reached and global outcomes are indicated.

Use Case 6: Proteomics for antibiotic susceptibility testing and molecular phenotyping of antibiotic resistant bacterial strains

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- O. Pible, Département Médicaments et Technologies pour la Santé (DMTS), CEA, INRAE, Université Paris-Saclay, F-30200 Bagnols-sur-Cèze. Bioinformatics for proteogenomics.

Objectives

The identification of bacteria is currently essentially carried out in the clinical microbiology laboratory based on the mass profile of ribosomal proteins detected by MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. However, although this approach is well suited for clinical isolates, it has strong limitations in cases of bacterial mixtures. It is often not suitable on biological samples without any culture step. It offers low performances for typing antibiotic resistant bacterial strains at the most resolved taxonomic level and does not give easy information on antibiotic resistances of the isolates. In this context, proteomics methods, based on the monitoring by liquid chromatography coupled to electrospray mass spectrometry of proteotypic peptides which can be inferred from genomic information stored in the ABRomics database could address these issues and provide relevant tools for antibiotic susceptibility testing. High-resolution targeted proteomics is a powerful approach to identify isolates and their expressed resistances, but requires to take into account the large heterogeneity of peptide sequences. Complementarily, untargeted discovery proteomic analyses (shotgun proteomics) could improve the structural annotation of bacterial genes involved in antibiotic resistance and strengthen the proteotypic peptide prioritization. The data (targeted proteomics, shotgun proteomics) will be supplied in the ABRomics database for a large dataset of relevant isolates. Specific bioinformatics tools will be developed for exploiting these data.

Outlines

Two complementary tasks will be undertaken from data stored in the ABRomics database: (i) automated exploitation of gene sequencing data for the design of targeted and quantitative proteomic methods for antibiotic susceptibility testing, and (ii) Proteogenomics insights into antibiotic gene resistance and virulence.

1. Automated exploitation of gene sequencing data for the design of targeted and quantitative proteomic methods for antibiotic susceptibility testing.

The aim is to perform a concordance analysis between proteomics and antibiograms for extended-spectrum beta-lactamase in clinical strains representative of epidemiology. Indeed, ESBL resistance mechanisms show a very high

allelic variability since several hundreds of protein isoforms are described combining the CTX-M, SHV et TEM families. Precise detection and quantification of each ESBL variant by a proteomics technology in strains collected either in a clinical setting or in the environment requires the development of a dedicated algorithm. The first stage of this algorithm development will be to list proteotypic tryptic peptides amenable to mass spectrometry detection.

2. Proteogenomics insights into antibiotic gene resistance and virulence.

The aims are to improve antibiotic gene resistance and bacterial genome annotation by proteogenomics data, and to predict expressed proteome profiles from any theoretical genome and detection of abnormal experimental protein profiles. Systematic search of peptides in experimental proteomic datasets could reinforce the annotation of genes and their appropriate delineation (Hartmann & Armengaud, 2014). A specific pipeline to confront pan-genomics data and pan-proteomics data should be specifically developed. The resulting improved annotated database will help for detection of pathogens and automatic characterization of their expressed resistances.

Tasks for UC6 supported by WP2 and WP3

1. Development of an algorithm for integrating genomics and proteomics datasets, and modifying genome annotation with experimental peptide information, and prediction of proteotypic peptides for targeted proteomics measurements. Support WP3
2. Proteomic analysis of 120 reference antibiotic resistant strains: submission of high-quality, top-annotated experimental label-free proteome datasets for 120 referenced strains to the ABRomics database with their antibiotics susceptibility extensive characterization. Support WP2

Deliverables for UC6

1. Prediction of proteotypic peptides for detectability of antibiotic resistance proteins and virulence factors.
2. A Standard Operating Procedure for proteomics datasets submission and proteogenomics interpretation.

